

Deliverable 6.2

Data Management Plan – Initial Version

QPL
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DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

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AUTHORS (Organisation)	Margarita Angelidou, Elli Roma-Athanasiadou, Christos Politis, George Vlachos (QPL); Efstratios Stylianidis (AUTH); Marta Macías Aragonés (CTA); Sergi Costa (BPRO); Jana Bielikova (PED); Áine Whelan (SRA); Mar Cátedra Cerón (CAP); Samir Sayadi (IFA)
REVIEWERS	Mar Cátedra Cerón (CAP), Samir Sayadi (IFA), Kallitsa Pantazi (RCM), Efstratios Stylianidis (AUTH)
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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CCRI-CSO	European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's Coordination and Support Office
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC or Commission	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EPP	Environmental Protection Planning tool
ESG	Environmental, Socioeconomic and Governance
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
MARC	Multi-Actor Regional Constellation
OAI	Open Archives Initiative
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PC	Project Coordinator
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMS	Policy Monitoring System

QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
SME	Small and Mid-size Enterprise
TL	Task Leader
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
WTL	Work Task Leader
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the initial version of the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** and has been elaborated as a deliverable (D6.2) in the framework of the ROBIN project. ROBIN sets out to empower Europe's regional authorities to fulfil their role as agents of just, inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. The project provides support to co-shape their governance structures and models in ways that accelerate the deployment of their **circular bioeconomy targets**, while also promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

In this context, the initial version of the project's DMP sets out the overall methodological principles pertaining to the management of the data that will be collected, generated and / or re-used in the framework of ROBIN, safeguarding sound and ethical data management along the entire duration of the project. Moreover, it provides a first, yet still meaningful overview of ROBIN's data, as identified in this early stage of the project, along with information on the methodology pertaining to their management as well as to making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).

The initial version of the DMP is the first of the three versions of ROBIN's Data Management Plan to be produced in the course of the project and will serve as a living document (D6.2 Data Management Plan – Initial Version delivered in M6 will be updated to D6.3 Data Management Plan – Interim Version in M18 and ultimately fixed as D6.4 Data Management Plan – Final Version in M36). Along these lines, the DMP will be updated and further elaborated during the project to reflect an accurate, up-to-date and ultimately comprehensive plan for managing the data that will be collected, generated and / or re-used by the project across their entire life cycle, both during and after the completion of ROBIN.

1. Introduction

The current document represents the initial version of ROBIN's Data Management Plan (DMP), which has received funding from the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon Europe under Grant Agreement No 101060504.

ROBIN aims to **empower Europe's Regions to adapt their governance models and structures to accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets** while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of just, inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. To this end, we establish and demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 European Regions within Ireland, **Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece**. ROBIN will provide them all the necessary support for networking and mutual learning, as well as a practical **digital Toolbox** to drive the operation of successful governance models. We will closely monitor and evaluate the project's performance, providing evidence of its economic, societal, and environmental impacts.

To this end, the **consortium** of ROBIN brings together a complementary and interdisciplinary group of **12 partners and 1 affiliated entity across 6 different countries** within the EU, as presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: ROBIN partners

Partner Role*	Partner No	Partner Name	Partner Short name	Country
CO	1	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	QPL	Greece
BEN	2	FUNDACION CORPORACION TECNOLOGICA DE ANDALUCIA	CTA	Spain
BEN	3	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR	Belgium
BEN	4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PED	Slovakia
BEN	5	STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	S2I	Germany
BEN	6	ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	ZSK	Slovakia
BEN	7	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	MTU	Ireland
BEN	8	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
BEN	9	REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	RCM	Greece
BEN	10	CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	CAP	Spain

Partner Role*	Partner No	Partner Name	Partner Short name	Country
AE	10.1	INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y FORMACIÓN AGRARIA, PESQUERA, ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCIÓN ECOLÓGICA	IFA	Spain
BEN	11	BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	BPRO	Germany
BEN	12	SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	SRA	Ireland

* CO = Coordinator, BEN= Beneficiaries, AE = Affiliated Entities

All partners of ROBIN's consortium adhere to sound data management principles in order to ensure that the meaningful data collected, generated and / or re-used throughout the duration of the project are well-managed, archived and preserved, in line with the structure and guidelines of the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template¹.

Along these lines, this initial version of the DMP aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Describe the data management lifecycle for the data to be collected, generated and / or re-used in the framework of ROBIN, serving as the key element of good data management.
- Outline the methodology employed to safeguard the sound management of the data collected, and/or generated as well as to make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).
- Provide information on the data that will be collected, generated and/or re-used and the way in which it will be handled during and after the end of the project along with the standards applied to this end.
- Describe details on how the data will be made openly accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders as well as its curation and preservation.
- Address the management of any research outputs other than data in line with FAIR principles.
- Present information on the resources to be allocated so as to make data FAIR clearly identifying responsibilities pertaining to data management, while addressing data security and ethical aspects.

With the above in mind, this initial version of **the DMP is structured in 8 distinct chapters**, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the DMP, the context in which it has been elaborated as well as its objectives and structure.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

- **Chapter 2** presents a summary of the data to be collected/generated or re-used during the activities of ROBIN including its purpose as well as its types and formats. Additionally, it outlines its origin, expected volume and the stakeholders that may find it useful.
- **Chapter 3** describes the methodology that is applied in ROBIN in order to safeguard the effective management of data across their entire lifecycle, making it FAIR.
- **Chapter 4** presents the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout ROBIN and provides sufficient details on making them FAIR.
- **Chapter 5** estimates the resources required for making the project's data FAIR, while also identifying data management responsibilities.
- **Chapter 6** outlines the data security strategy applied within the context of ROBIN along with the respective secure storage solutions employed.
- **Chapter 7** addresses ethical aspects as well as other relevant issues pertaining to the data collected/generated or re-used during the implementation of the project.
- **Chapter 8** concludes on the next steps foreseen in the framework of the project with respect to its data management plan.

Annexed in the document are (i) the project's Privacy Policy (Annex I), the templates for the (ii) Informed Consent Form (Annex II) and (iii) the Data Subject Request Form (Annex III) as well as (iv) the Record of Processing Activities (Annex IV) which will be used during the implementation of the project's activities to ensure compliance with relevant applicable EU and national regulation(s).

Note that the **DMP is not a fixed document**. It evolves during the lifespan of the project and **will be further elaborated and updated at least twice more throughout the duration of ROBIN (i.e., as D6.3 at M18 and D6.4 at M36)**. Additional ad hoc updates may also be realised (if necessary), in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect changes in the methodology or other aspects relevant to their management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors. QPL is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP and with the support of all partners will update and enrich it when required.

2. Data summary

ROBIN will collect/generate or re-use meaningful non-sensitive data that do not fall into any special categories² of personal data as those are described within the General Data Protection Regulation³ (GDPR). These data may be quantitative, qualitative or a blend of those in nature and will be analysed from a range of methodological perspectives with a view to producing insights that will successfully feed ROBIN's activities, enable us to deliver evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project. With that in mind, the second chapter of the Data Management Plan (DMP) starts by explaining the purpose for which this data will be collected/generated and how it relates with ROBIN. It proceeds by describing the different types and formats of this data as well as its origin and expected volume, before concluding with an overview of potential stakeholders for whom it may prove useful for re-use.

2.1 Purpose of data collection / generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project

In order to successfully meet its objectives and ensure the production of evidence-based results, ROBIN entails several activities during which data will be collected/generated or re-used. The purpose for which this data is collected/generated or re-used is interrelated with the objective of the activity during which it is produced.

In particular, these activities along with their objectives in the framework of ROBIN are as follows:

1. **Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC)** in each target region, in order to gather representatives from all related sections, in particular from the local government, the business community, the academic institutions, the primary biomass producers, and the civil society.
2. **Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance**, to understand the state of play in the current ROBIN regions circular bioeconomy policy landscape and to ultimately feed into the regions' governance profiles developed under T1.4
3. **Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions** to put in context the types of regional governance models in Europe, while accounting for different policy & socio-technical contexts.

² Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

4. **Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy**, in order to create an inventory of applied regional bioeconomy governance models.
5. **Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions**, identifying barriers and opportunities to deepen our understanding of their regional context, their positioning regarding circularity and bioeconomy policies, their governance systems and their strategies' targets and values.
6. **Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders** to help develop new and improved governance models focusing on circular bioeconomy.
7. **Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region** to provide them with tailored action plans considering their particular needs.
8. **Development of the ROBIN Tools** to help to address the improvement areas in governance, to support the new governance models and structures identified in T2.1 and to guide the integration of regional opportunities towards the implementation of circular bioeconomy.
9. **Data collected/generated by the utilisation of the ROBIN Toolbox**, which aggregates the project's tools and supports actions in order to facilitate the implementation of sustainable bio-based value chains.
10. **Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans** that will help the set-up and operation of the new circular bioeconomy governance structures, with a view to guiding the testing and validation of the ROBIN toolbox in two rounds.
11. **Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox** in order to collect valuable feedback from stakeholders across our target regions that will be utilised in evaluating and validating our toolbox in Task 3.3. The stakeholders will derive from the regional governance structures and will include MARC members for the Alpha testing and will derive from regional authorities outside of the consortium for the Beta testing.
12. **Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox**, in order to draw meaningful conclusions on areas of improvement for the Toolbox and its components, utilising the experience and expertise of our Advisory Board.
13. **Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change**, in order to spot any inefficiencies or place for improvement and provide continuous feed to the evaluation process.
14. **Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions**, to promote the development of cross-regional partnerships on regional bioeconomy, exchange knowledge, reach out to bigger audiences and promote engagement.
15. **Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations** to provide EU and European Regions the know-how regarding setting in motion new regional governance models and structures for the circular bioeconomy.
16. **Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities** of ROBIN with a view to measuring their results and impact, fine-tune ROBIN's Dissemination and Communication Plan, as well as fulfil the project's reporting requirements towards the Commission.
17. **Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board.**

18. **Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives**, in order to coordinate, develop and benefit from synergies with other relevant EU initiatives and to establish a close collaboration with the project BIOMODEL4REGIONS.

The following section provides further details on the different types and formats of data collected/generated or re-used during the project's activities.

2.2 Types and formats of collected / generated or re-used data

ROBIN is set to collect / generate or re-use data of various structures and formats. Along these lines, the data definition process used for this DMP is based on the source and the physical format of the data⁴. In particular, we define two main aspects: (i) the process under which the underlying data are created / captured which includes electronic text documents, spreadsheets, questionnaires and transcripts, among others and (ii) the storage format of quantitative and qualitative data. Examples of this aspect include easily accessible formats, such as postscripts (e.g., pdf, xps, etc.), machine readable formats (xml, html, etc.), spreadsheets, (e.g., xls, csv, etc.), text documents (e.g., docx, rtf, etc.), compressed formats (e.g., rar, zip, etc.) or any other format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the framework of which it is produced.

Under this framework, special attention will be paid in using **open formats**⁵ (such as csv, pdf, zip, etc.) and / or **machine-readable formats**⁶ (such as xml, json, rdf, html, etc.) when possible, to enhance the **interoperability** and **re-use** of data. In doing so, we will be providing data that is **easily readable** and **freely usable in any software program** employed by third parties interested in utilizing the data.

The type and formats of the data collected / generated in the context of ROBIN can be divided into **3 categories**, namely (i) data collected / generated by direct input methods; (ii) data collected / generated through use of the ROBIN Toolbox; and (iii) data collected / generated from dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and clustering activities, as described in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Data collected / generated through direct input methods

Direct input methods, under the scope of ROBIN, involve methodologies for collecting data through desk research and interactions between consortium partners and external stakeholders, with the latter providing data to the former. Along these lines, external stakeholders undertake the role of a data subject that is a natural person whose personal data is being processed⁷. In particular, the identification and selection of suitable data subjects are based on purposeful sampling according to

⁴ Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>.

⁵ According to the *Open Data Handbook*: "An open format is a file format with no restrictions, monetary or otherwise, placed upon its use and can be fully processed with at least one free/open-source software tool and it is not encumbered by any copyrights, patents, trademarks or other restrictions so that anyone may use it".

⁶ According to the *Open Data Handbook*: "Machine readable formats are file formats that can be automatically read and processed by a computer. Machine-readable data must be structured data".

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>.

which, external stakeholders are identified and selected by consortium partners based on their role regarding grounding circular bioeconomy policies in regional governance structures (e.g., individuals involved in implementing and designing regional bioeconomy strategies, stakeholders from local government, business community, academic institutions, primary biomass producers, and civil society, etc.) and the objectives of the respective activity for which data is collected. In this context, quantitative and qualitative data will be collected / generated during ROBIN⁸:

- **Quantitative data** is numerical and acquired through counting or measuring. Examples of quantitative data are the yearly turnovers of a business, the hourly compensation of a worker, the number of SMEs in Europe, etc. This data may be represented by ordinal, interval or ratio scales and lend themselves to statistical manipulation.
- **Qualitative data**, sometimes referred to as categorical data, is data that can be arranged into categories based on physical traits, gender, colours or anything that does not have a number associated with it. Moreover, written documents, interviews, and various forms of in-field observation are all sources of qualitative data. Examples of qualitative data are the preferences of learning, skillsets, country of origin, etc.

Additional details with respect to the different types and formats of data that will be collected through direct input methods under the frame of ROBIN are provided below.

1. Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations

The data deriving by this activity fall under Task 1.1 (WR) and will include information on the candidate MARC members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile). They will be collected by the consortium partners, under the guidance of WR, following the process of retrieving information from online public sources (professional websites, etc). The collection/generation processes that will be used to capture these data include the identification of suitable relevant stakeholders by each partner's region. The partners will provide the consortium with information that is publicly available. Once the selection process is concluded through shortlisting and voting, the partner who recommended each person will contact them to formally invite them to consent to participating as a MARC member. The data are going to be qualitative and they will be stored in text documents, spreadsheets and image files (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg).

2. Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance

The data to be collected/generated in the framework of this activity fall under Task 1.1 (WR) and will include the opinions of the MARC members on the barriers, opportunities, and incentives that the regional actors have when engaging in circular bioeconomy. They will originate from semi-structured interviews and will include qualitative and quantitative data, stored in text documents and spreadsheets (interview transcripts, notes, minutes, questionnaires) in .docx and .xlsx format.

3. Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions

The data to be collected in the framework of this activity fall under Task 1.2 (AUTH) and will include information about specific characteristics of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models found in European Regions. The analysis of this data will generate a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy

⁸ Neuman, W. L. (2014). Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches. Boston: Pearson.

Governance Models in the EU. The collected and generated data will be qualitative and quantitative and will be stored in text documents and spreadsheets and the storage format will include .docx, .xlsx, pdf and web links.

4. Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy

The data deriving from this activity will include an inventory of 50 regional good practices and the identification and in-depth analysis of 10 cases of regional government actions towards circular bioeconomy and fall under Task 1.3 (MTU). The data will be collected through desk research and will include qualitative and quantitative data. They will be stored in text documents and spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx, pdf, web links).

5. Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions

The data to be collected/generated here belong to Task 1.4 (AUPh) and will include insights into attributes of the regional policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions, as well as views and perceptions regarding the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy. The methods of data collection will include desk research and semi-structured interviews with individuals involved in the design and implementation of such strategies. The data will be qualitative and quantitative and will include profiles of the regions and written minutes of the interviews typically stored in a standard text document (.docx), as well as spreadsheets (.xlsx).

6. Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders

This activity's data will be collected/generated within the framework of Task 2.1 (CTA) and will include the outcomes of the co-creation activities designed to engage the MARC members and collect their insights on the elements needed to create governance models and practices that help regions overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy. The data (qualitative and quantitative) will originate out of co-creative sessions and a co-creation workshop taking place in each region. The notes and spreadsheets including qualitative and quantitative data, will be stored in formats such as .docx and .xlsx.

7. Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region

The data to be collected/generated in the framework of this activity fall under Task 2.2 (CTA) and will result in two data sets. The first data set is a portfolio of support actions for regional capacity building focusing on key areas to be taken into account. The portfolio will build upon the results provided by the co-creation workshops of the activity "Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders", together with results from literature research. The second data set will consist of the results of a workshop taking place within T2.2 to engage regional partners in shaping the Action plans of their regions. The data will be mainly qualitative and will be stored in text documents and spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx)

8. Development of the ROBIN Tools

The data to be collected/generated here belong to Task 2.3 (MTU) and derive from desk research and literature review of previous relevant projects that will help gather the elements to synthesise the three ROBIN tools including (i) the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas with the aim to help the 5 regions to develop and update their circular bioeconomy governance models; (ii) the Policy Monitoring System (PMS) tool to help regional authorities evaluate their governance model performance regarding circular bioeconomy standards with the prospect of taking actions for its overall optimisation; and (iii) the Environmental Protection Planning tool (EPP) to help the regions

identify non-environmentally friendly practices across their policies, while assessing their regional footprint and working towards improvement actions by including appropriate practices in the regional governance models and their bio-based value chains. The data will be qualitative and quantitative and the data storage formats will include text documents as well as spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx).

9. Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans

This activity's data fall under the scope of Task 3.1 (BPRO) and will result in customized plans per region created by the regional partners and their support partners under the guidance of BPRO. The data will be qualitative and will include for each region: (i) the contact details of the members of the consortium teams to administer the regional governance structures; (ii) the list of activities envisaged to test the toolbox and the timing they will be deployed; (iii) the list of tools, functionalities and governance roadmaps that will be put under testing; (iv) the contact details of the members of the teams that will deploy the testing. The data storage formats will include text documents as well as spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf) or whatever format needed to secure the efficient and effective implementation of this task.

10. Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox

This activity's data will be collected/generated within the framework of Task 3.2 (BPRO) and will include quantitative and qualitative data on stakeholders' opinions regarding the application of ROBIN Toolbox in real-life settings across our target regions. The data will be gathered in two testing cycles: the first (alpha) engaging stakeholders of the regional governance structures and the second (beta) engaging stakeholders of regional authorities outside our consortium. Moreover, insights will be gathered by stakeholders engaging in 2 support action events that will be deployed in each region. The data that will be collected/generated here will feed Task 3.3. The storage format includes text documents and spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf) or whatever format needed to secure the personal data management protection guidelines.

11. Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox

The data to be collected/generated in the framework of this activity fall under Task 3.3 (S2I) and will include the conclusions of analysing and validating the data collected by the testings of T3.2 through the elaboration of a validation workshop engaging the Advisory Board (AB) members. More specifically the data (qualitative and quantitative) will include measures of the successful operation of the ROBIN Toolbox and suggestions for its fine-tuning, as well as insights that will be utilised in the creation of the support actions portfolio by CTA. The data storage format includes text documents and spreadsheets (docx, .xlsx, .pdf).

12. Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change

The data that will be collected/generated by this activity belong to Task 4.1 (PED) and are quantitative and qualitative data on the indicators set within this task. They will include measures of change, success and impact, findings and conclusions, ideas, opinions, useful information, past experiences and suggestions regarding the 5 regions. The data will be collected through the methods prescribed by the monitoring and assessment framework (that may include interviews, questionnaires, online surveys and reports etc.) and by a final round of interviews with the MARCs members (4 per region). The data storage formats will include text documents as well as spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx).

13. Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions

The data to be collected/generated here belong to Task 4.2 (CTA) and regard workshop and event results on regional bioeconomy policy implementation, including past experiences, suggestions, useful information, ideas, and opinions (in qualitative and quantitative form). The data will be collected through physical and virtual events at national level, mutual learning workshops and missions, as well as a Train-the-Trainer event, that will help regions exchange best practices and lessons learned. The data storage formats will include text documents and spreadsheets (.docx, .xlsx).

14. Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations

This activity's data fall under the scope of Task 4.3 (PED) and include the gathering of opinions, best practices and past experiences that will on the one hand constitute meaningful policy recommendations on how the EU and European Regions can support the realisation of the circular bioeconomy potential, and on the other hand feed a White paper and a guide on operationalising new governance models and structures, on requirements for coordinating with the CCRI-CSO, on good practices (utilising the results of T1.3) and on mutual learning and knowledge exchange. The data will be qualitative and will be gathered through desk research, and by accumulating lessons learned and good practices throughout the project's implementation. The data storage formats will include text documents (.docx).

15. Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board

The data regarding the setup of the ROBIN AB fall under Task 5.2 (WR) and include personal information of candidate AB members (e.g., name and surname, gender, organisation, position, email, country of placement, brief description of professional profile). They will be collected by the consortium partners, under the guidance of WR, following the process of retrieving information from online public sources (professional websites, etc). Each partner will be asked to identify 2-3 suitable relevant stakeholders from their own network and provide to the consortium information that is publicly available. The candidates will be assessed by a selection process and will be formally approached and invited to give their consent to become members of the AB. The data will be qualitative and stored in text document, image and spreadsheet format (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg).

16. Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives

The data deriving by this activity fall under Task 5.3 (S2I) and regard photos, number of event participants and presentations, meeting minutes, past knowledge and good practises deriving from the partners' synergetic actions with project BIOMODEL4REGIONS, as well as other relevant EU initiatives and the collaboration with the CCRI. The synergies and how they will be forged to benefit the ROBIN project activities will be decided, per case, based on discussions with representatives of these projects. The data (qualitative and quantitative) will be stored in text documents, spreadsheets, presentation, and image files (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg, .png). Additionally, some information will be available online on ROBIN's and collaboration partners' websites and social media.

Data collected/generated through direct input methods will be **stored in formats which allow the documentation of information from various files and documents in a single location**. By doing so, it is possible to circulate raw data from transcripts, as well as text, images, and other objects from other files to one document file or multiple tabs of a single spreadsheet. Moreover, these formats can be immediately converted into open and machine-readable formats (e.g. .xml

and .csv) boosting the interoperability and re-usability of the data produced in the framework of ROBIN.

2.2.2 *Data collected / generated by the utilisation of the ROBIN Toolbox*

In the context of ROBIN's Task 2.4 "Development of ROBIN Toolbox for the Implementation of Circular Bioeconomy Strategies", a digital toolbox will be created and will be made available on the project's website, by digitalising the:

- i) **ROBIN knowledge platform** (deriving by T1.2 and depicting different types of regional bioeconomy governance models and good practices)
- ii) **ROBIN Tools** (deriving by T2.2 and including the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas, the Policy Monitoring System tool, and the Environmental Protection Planning tool)
- iii) **ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio** (deriving by T2.2)

The ROBIN Toolbox aims to aggregate the project's tools and services in order to facilitate the implementation of sustainable bio-based value chains, to support the development, evaluation and improvement of governance models as well as the identification and mitigation of non-environmentally friendly practices and to be the main means of information, evaluation and provision of ROBIN's support actions. In this context, users of various roles, such as regional authorities, regional policy makers, people designing and implementing circular bioeconomy governance models, researchers in the field of bioeconomy, and regional stakeholders etc., are expected to utilize the functionalities offered by the ROBIN Toolbox which in their turn will generate valuable data for the project's 5 regions, as well as for the EU regions using it.

Along these lines, data collected by the users of the ROBIN Toolbox will include data that users of the Toolbox will provide in order to register, create a profile and use the Toolbox (information such as name, contact details, location and organisation). It also includes data generated based on tracking the activity of users across the ROBIN Toolbox that will be utilised for identifying areas for improvement. The goal is to support a data-driven process for improving the Toolbox by identifying processes that need enhancements and/or functionalities that are of low or no interest that could be deprecated. Activity data will be collected for all roles and stand to not only streamline processes and functionalities, but also allow the partners to identify the most prominent features required and utilised by participants, which will subsequently support the activities of the project regarding the accumulation of typologies, the creation, testing and evaluation of regional governance models and practices on bioeconomy and the knowledge exchange among regions in an EU level, fostering the sustainability of the ROBIN Toolbox.

The following sections (1,2, 3, 4 & 5) provide further details on data collected and/or generated from the use of the different constituent tools comprising the ROBIN Toolbox. The Task leader considered that it is too early at this point to provide a more detailed description/estimation. More information will be provided in the interim version of the DMP.

1. *ROBIN knowledge platform*

The knowledge platform will aggregate the different types of regional bioeconomy governance models and good governance practices per type of model and will aim to facilitate their discovery and inspire their application across Europe. The EU regions will be able to use this tool for learning and replicating governance good practices.

2. ROBIN Tools: (i) Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

The Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas is a strategic tool that can be used by the 5 regions for developing and updating their circular bioeconomy governance models. It will collect data about the regions' governance model's value proposition, beneficiaries, activities, partnerships, infrastructure and resources, cost structure and sustainability related costs and benefits.

3. ROBIN Tools: (ii) Policy Monitoring System (PMS) tool

The Policy Monitoring System tool will provide regional authorities with a means of evaluation to measure the performance of their governance model with respect to Environmental, Socioeconomic and Governance (ESG), public engagement, ethics, as well as territorial RRI aspects. The qualitative and quantitative data collected here aim to provide an overview that will help regional authorities take corrective action to optimize their governance model toward a more effective and responsible bioeconomy strategy.

4. ROBIN Tools: (iii) Environmental Protection Planning (EPP) tool

The Environmental Protection Planning tool will allow Regional Authorities to detect non-environmentally friendly practices across environmental management areas and to prevent/mitigate adverse effects during the implementation of their circular bioeconomy policy. It will be used as a guide to develop tailored EPPs and training sessions based on their requirements, also utilising the BERural educational material. This tool will gather data to assess the regional footprint through environmental performance indicators (waste, emissions, natural bio-based resources, environmental management, etc.).

The tool will link the assessment results with the appropriate action plans and training sessions with the overall aim to ensure a better environmental footprint within the bio-based value chains of a region. The improved environmental practices will be linked with the regional governance models securing the long-term implementation of sustainable value chains and circular bioeconomy.

5. ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio

The Support Actions Portfolio will help tailor the support actions and plans of each of the 5 project regions, so that they tend to their specificities and needs. Regional authorities can use it as a filter to identify the actions addressing their unique circumstances. Indicatively the topics the portfolio might address could include the following:

- use of ROBIN tools
- raising regional / local actor awareness
- development of a regional cluster of stakeholders
- government support to enhance circularity in business
- implementation of good practices
- integrating opportunities in regional bioeconomy domain
- training for deploying environmental protection plans
- social innovation methodologies, tools and applications

More information regarding the tools of the ROBIN Toolbox and the data collected / generated through their use will be provided in future updates of the DMP, as their functionalities are further specified and developed in line with the findings stemming from the project's studies and activities.

2.2.3 *Data collected / generated from dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities*

The data deriving by monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication results of the project and by the stakeholder engagement with a view to measuring the impact of the relevant activities, fall under Task 5.1 (WR) and include (i). Website analytics; (ii) social media statistics (including Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn); (iii). Data collected from project events; (iv). Newsletter subscriptions and (v) Data collected from dissemination and communication activities (e.g., participation in external events, participation in project workshops, etc.). The data will be identified through online analytics, utilising google analytics, SMAs, partners reporting, Mailchimp platform, etc. WR is responsible for sending the necessary templates (.docx, .xlsx) to all partners, alongside with guidelines on how to fill them in, as well as for collecting input on an ad-hoc basis (i.e., each time a dissemination or stakeholder engagement action is performed). WR is also responsible for preparing the necessary reports to evaluate the overall progress of dissemination and communication activities (measuring outcomes against pre-set KPIs) throughout the lifespan of the project. The storage format of the data to be collected during the project's duration, includes .csv, .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg and .png files.

1. Website analytics:

The ROBIN website was developed during the first months of the project (it was launch on the 19/12/22 – M4) and will be the main dissemination channel of the project, hosting the deliverables and links to the tools, providing information about the project, partners, and regions, as well as sharing news with a dedicated section and a newsletter. Two sets of data will be collected within this category:

- Visitors' statistics (anonymised data), through Google Analytics
- Newsletter subscribers, through MailChimp.

This type of information will be mostly used for reporting purposes. Data will be stored in spreadsheets (.xlsx) while the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard text document (.docx).

When people will visit the ROBIN website, it will (via cookies - as in the case of every online website) automatically collect information about the visitor's device used for accessing the website (e.g., web browser, IP address, time zone). Additionally, information will be captured on how visitors interact with the website itself. We refer to this, automatically collected, information as "Device Information".

2. Social Media statistics (including Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn):

These data will be collected/generated through a periodic monitoring of the project's social media statistics (i.e., Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn) with a view to measuring and assessing the performance and results of the project's social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication. With that in mind, the data will be both qualitative as well as quantitative in nature addressing the metrics reached on each channel (e.g., number of followers, tweets impressions on Twitter, friends, likes on Facebook, number of people reached through posts, etc.). Additionally, these data will be followed by an analysis of the results stemming from them and possible ways to improve the results so as to reach the project's targets. All in all, the data will be stored in a spreadsheet (.xlsx) while at the same time the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard text document (.docx).

3. *Data collected from project events*

These data will be collected during the implementation of the project through: (i) the different events (e.g. co-creation workshops, validation workshop, train-the-trainer event, interviews, physical and virtual events, etc.) organised by ROBIN (either alone or jointly with other projects or initiatives) consisting of the participants' lists that will enclose demographic information about the participants; and (ii) the participation of ROBIN partners in relevant third party events in order to reach out and engage stakeholders, thus collecting general information about the events attended and their outreach.

Along these lines, these data will be collected so as to keep track of the results of activities in events for stakeholder engagement and provide the opportunity to project partners to report on these activities. Moreover, these data will be updated every time a partner attends an event, or a partner organises an event. Finally, the data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx).

4. *Newsletter subscriptions*

In order to enhance the dissemination activities of the project, newsletter subscriptions are foreseen on the project's website. A subscription form hosted on the project's website will facilitate the collection of these data. Any interested stakeholder can voluntarily provide their contact details in a dedicated sign-up form, so as to receive the most up-to-date news and outcomes of the project. A newsletter will be sent to subscribers once per 6 months. These data will be collected so as interested stakeholders can be informed about ROBIN, as well as its Toolbox. Along these lines, the data will be comprised of a list of subscribers along with their basic contact information: (i) email address, (ii) first and last name, (iii) country, (iv) type of organisation, (v) region and (vi) gender. A copy of this contact list will be stored on MailChimp's (<http://mailchimp.com>) server, which is used for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. All personal information included in this contact list is used and protected according to MailChimp's Privacy Policy.

5. *Data collected from dissemination and communication activities*

These data will be collected through the periodic monitoring of the project's miscellaneous dissemination activities such as publications in relevant journals, posts in blogs, etc. The data will consist of a spreadsheet designed to keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activity, including, but not limited to, press releases, social media posts, website articles, interviews, events (conferences, meetings, workshops, etc.), other publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. The purpose of collecting these data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project. For this purpose, a template will be shared with all partners to recommend activities to be performed and log the activities they performed. The template is provided also online so as the partners can directly update their input. Finally, all the data will be integrated into a single spreadsheet (.xlsx).

2.3 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

In the context of ROBIN, **new data** will be collected/generated by partners as well as external stakeholders participating in the activities of the project and/or using its Toolbox. With that in mind and aside consortium partners, **external groups of stakeholders from which new data will originate include:**

- Regional authorities within and outside the EU
- Business community (advisors engaging in bio-based industry, primary biomass producers)

- Major European Initiatives (e.g., CCRI)
- Relevant Initiatives (EU projects focusing on bioeconomy, bioeconomy networks and working groups);
- Policy makers at regional, national and EU level (related to bioeconomy governance models)
- Academic experts in the field of bioeconomy and regional development (e.g., within academic institutions, non-university public research organisations, research and innovation organisations etc.).
- Consultants, such as regional development advisory companies.

Moreover, **pre-existing data** will be utilised within the context of ROBIN as well. In particular, outputs from EU-funded projects (e.g., POWER4BIO, ICT-BIOCHAIN MPowerBIO, SUPERBIO, BIOCHAIN, BIOSWITCH, Transition2BIO, RRI2SCALE, MARIE etc.), national projects, institutions and other relevant initiatives in a large extent will provide a solid basis for ROBIN. The ROBIN consortium will strive to make the most of and advance the work and results of these projects. Such activities include the development of the ROBIN Toolbox and more specifically the ROBIN Knowledge platform and the ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio. The whole development process of the typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions and the creation of the portfolio of support actions of the ROBIN Toolbox, builds upon the pre-existing knowledge, methodologies and outputs of other projects, initiatives, relevant institutions and policies. Finally, consortium partners' internal knowledge, experience and expertise from their participation in other projects and initiatives will directly and indirectly support the implementation of activities throughout the project.

2.4 Expected size of data

ROBIN entails a series of activities aiming at setting the stage for and ultimately facilitating the development, piloting, evaluation, validation and fine-tuning of the ROBIN toolbox and support services. With that in mind, the table that follows presents the different activities implemented during the course of the project in which data are collected/generated, the types and formats of the data as well as the expected size of the data.

Table 2: Expected size of data

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Expected size of data (KB)*
1	Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	Information of candidate MARC members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile)	Notes, spreadsheets, images	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg	40.000 KB
2	Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance	Multi-Actor Regional Constellation opinions on barriers, opportunities, and incentives	Interview Notes, Minutes, Questionnaires, Spreadsheets	.docx/ .xlsx	600.000 KB

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Expected size of data (KB)*
3	Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions	Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions	Spreadsheets, notes	.docx, .xlsx, pdf, web links	1.000 KB
4	Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy	Inventory of 50 good regional practices and analysis of 10 cases of regional government actions towards circular bioeconomy.	Spreadsheets, notes, interview transcripts	.docx, .xlsx, pdf, web links	200.000 KB
5	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Insights into attributes of the regional policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions, as well as views and perceptions regarding the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy.	Spreadsheets, Notes, Interview transcripts	.docx, .xlsx	1000 KB
6	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	MARC's insights on the elements needed to create governance models and practices that help regions overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy.	Notes, minutes, Recordings	.docx, .xlsx, .mp3, .mp4	85.000 KB
7	Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region	Portfolio of support actions for regional capacity building and regional partners' insights regarding the support actions needed in their region.	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx, .xlsx	45.000 KB
8	Development of the ROBIN Tools	"Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas, Policy Monitoring System tool and Environmental Protection Planning tool."	Notes, spreadsheets, questionnaires	.docx, .xlsx, ppt, pdf	200.000 KB

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Expected size of data (KB)*
9	Data collected/generated by the utilisation of the ROBIN Toolbox	ROBIN knowledge platform	User-generated/ machine-generated	TBD ⁹	About 150.000 KB
		Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas	User-generated/ machine-generated	.docx, .ppt, .pdf ⁹	About 150.000 KB
		Policy Monitoring System tool	User-generated/ machine-generated	.docx, .xlsx, .ppt, .pdf ⁹	About 150.000 KB
		Environmental Protection Planning tool	User-generated/ machine-generated	.docx, .xlsx, .ppt, .pdf ⁹	About 150.000 KB
		ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio	User-generated/ machine-generated	TBD ⁹	About 150.000 KB
10	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	responsible teams, list and timeline of activities to be deployed, list of tools to be tested, teams that will take part in both alpha and beta testing	Spreadsheets, Online questionnaires, Interview transcripts, Notes	.xlsx, .docx, .pdf	70.000 KB
11	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Quantitative and qualitative data on stakeholders' opinions regarding the application of ROBIN Toolbox in real life settings across our target regions; registration lists of 2 support action events	User generated/ machine generate, notes, spreadsheets	.xlsx, .docx, .pdf	350.000 KB
12	Evaluation and Validation of Testing	Measures of successful operation of the Toolbox, suggestions for fine-tuning it,	Notes, spreadsheets	.xlsx, .docx	About 150.000 KB

⁹ As also mentioned in section 2.2.2, the Task leader considered that it is too early at this point to provide a more detailed description/estimation. More information will be provided in the interim version of the DMP.

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Expected size of data (KB)*
	Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox	and insights to be utilised in the creation of the support actions portfolio			
13	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Measures of success and impact, conclusions, ideas, opinions, useful information, past experiences and suggestions	Notes, spreadsheets	.xlsx, .docx, .pdf	2.000 KB
14	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Workshop and event results on regional bioeconomy policy implementation, past experiences, suggestions, useful information, ideas, opinions	Notes, spreadsheets	.xlsx, .docx, .pdf	60.000 KB
15	Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations	Opinions, Best practices, Past experiences	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx	800 KB
16	Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities	Website and social media analytics	User generated/ machine generated	.csv, .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg, .png	About 200.000 KB
		Data collected from project events	Spreadsheets	.xlsx	100.000 KB
		Data collected from dissemination and communication actions	Spreadsheets, images	.csv, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg, .png, .docx	100.000 KB
		Newsletter subscriptions	Spreadsheets	.csv, .xlsx	100.000 KB
17	Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	Information of candidate AB members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile)	Notes, spreadsheets, images	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg	100.000 KB

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Expected size of data (KB)*
18	Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives	Photos, number of event participants, presentations, joint activities	Notes, spreadsheets, images, presentations	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg, .png	About 50.000 KB

* The estimated expected size of the data is based on the adjusted size of data generated via similar activities of project partners in the past unless otherwise indicated.

2.5 Data utility

The stakeholders that may find meaningful utility for the data to be collected/generated or re-used by the project (both within as well as outside of ROBIN's consortium) along with the benefits that could arise for them by utilizing these data, are concisely presented in the table that follows.

Table 3: Data utility

Stakeholder group	Data utility
Policy makers at regional, national and EU level related to circular bioeconomy	The aim of ROBIN is to support the 5 participating regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece to find the ways and means to reach their potential regarding co-shaping their governance structures and models in ways that will help them fulfil their circular bioeconomy targets. The typological analysis of governance models and structures in different regional settings, the co-creation of a digital Toolbox to drive the circular bioeconomy transition and the co-creation of meaningful policy recommendations are going to be very useful for regions around the world that wish to pursue the same endeavours. More specifically the projects generated data and results will offer policy makers the tools to create improved, more inclusive and better-informed governance models based on stakeholder engagement, as well as insights into local potentialities along with the means to tap into them for stimulating bio-based innovation. Along these lines, data generated to this end, may be of great utility for experts who design, implement and/or fund relevant policies. Data generated on designated policy activities (policy briefs) will provide meaningful input that could be used to inform the design of policies targeted in circular bioeconomy regional governance around the world.
Bio-based industry, advisors & investors	The data created/ generated through ROBIN will provide insights on how to accomplish networking and stakeholder engagement to build the connections required to accelerate bio-based innovation. The results of the project are expected to increase awareness regarding bioeconomy and its benefits and to provide useful feedback on a policy making level regarding integrating bio-based value chain development into broader policies and regional development plans. To this end, data generated through ROBIN, may be of great utility for industry

	advisors and investors engaging in the implementation and funding of relevant policies.
Scientific community	In the frame of the ROBIN project, interdisciplinary research is performed that largely builds upon prior research efforts to generate insights on regional bioeconomy models and structures across Europe. Additionally, local stakeholders are engaged in the project's co-creation, mutual learning, testing and validation activities, mapping a plethora of perspectives regarding the state of play in advancing circular bioeconomy governance in European regions. Research data of the project that will be published in reports or peer-reviewed scientific journals as well as deposited in open repositories can be of great utility for scientists in the field, aggregating and classifying existing scientific knowledge on types of bioeconomy governance models and creating new knowledge and empirical open data on the application of novel inclusive governance models.
Civil society	ROBIN aims to engage local stakeholders in its core activities in order to make sure that their perspective is taken into consideration in regional policies, and to find more meaningful ways and develop tools to address their needs and to empower them in engaging in regional bioeconomy governance and policy making.
Project partners	The data collected/generated during ROBIN is the cornerstone for project partners in order to produce evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project. Indeed, these data enable the co-creation, testing and validation of regional models and plans, as well as useful tools (ROBIN Toolbox) that will help embed bioeconomy policies in regional and territorial agendas. At the same time, these data may be meaningful for project partners beyond the end of the project as well, enabling them to build and capitalise upon interesting ideas and opportunities that may emerge to ensure the long-term sustainability of the ROBIN methodology and Toolbox.

3. FAIR data

The guidelines on Data Management Plan¹⁰ of the Commission emphasise the importance of making the data produced by projects funded under Horizon Europe **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable as well as Reusable (FAIR)**, with a view to ensuring its sound management. This means using standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data. With that in mind, the following sections of the DMP lay out the methodology followed in the framework of ROBIN with respect to making data findable, accessible and interoperable as well as ensuring their preservation and open access, with a view to increasing its re-use.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Data discoverability and identification mechanisms

ROBIN places special emphasis on enhancing the discoverability of the data collected/generated or re-used during the course of its activities. **Open data produced during the implementation of the project will be locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism.** Indeed, ROBIN will be able to assign globally resolvable **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)** on any open data (more information on open data as well as the respective repositories we plan on employing in the context of the project are provided in section 3.2). An identifier is a unique identification code that is applied to a dataset, so that it can be unambiguously referenced. For example, a catalogue number is an identifier for a particular specimen and an ISBN code is an identifier for a particular book. PIDs are simply maintainable identifiers that allow for permanent reference to a digital object. In other words, PIDs are a way of giving digital resources, such as documents, images and data records, a unique and persistent reference number.

At the same time, data that are not open will be deposited in a searchable resource (i.e., the cloud web storage service of the project) and well-tailored identification mechanisms will be utilized as well, in the form of standard naming conventions that will safeguard their consistency and make them easily locatable for partners within the frame of the project. Along these lines, the following subsection provides further analysis on naming conventions and versioning.

3.1.2 Naming conventions and versioning

Following a consistent set of naming conventions in the development of the project's data files can greatly enhance their searchability. With that in mind, ROBIN creates consistent data file names that provide clues to their content, status and versioning, while also increasing their discoverability. In doing so, project partners as well as interested stakeholders can easily identify a file as well as classify and sort them.

According to the UK Data Archive ([UK Data Service, 2017b](#)), a best practice in naming convention is to create brief yet meaningful names for data files, that facilitate classification. The naming

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

convention should avoid the utilisation of spaces, dots and special characters (such as & or !), whereas the use of underscores is endorsed, to separate elements in the data file name and make them understandable. At the same time, versioning should be a part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file.

With that in mind and to facilitate the reference of the datasets that will be produced during its implementation, ROBIN employs a **standard naming convention that integrates versioning and takes into account the possibility of creating multiple datasets** during an activity that entails data collection/generation. Indeed, ROBIN's naming convention considers this issue and addresses it by employing a unique element that captures the number of datasets that are produced under the same activity.

In particular, the **naming convention employed by the project is described below.**

[Name of project] _ [Name of Study] _ [Number of dataset] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- **Name of project:** ROBIN
- **Name of Study:** A short version of the name of the activity for which the dataset is created.
- **Number of dataset:** An indication of the number assigned to the dataset.
- **Issue Date:** The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (YYYY.MM.DD.).
- **Version number:** The versioning number of a dataset.

With the above in mind, some **indicative examples** to showcase the naming structure that will be applied in the context of ROBIN are provided below:

- **ROBIN_BarriersOpportunities&Motivations_Dataset1_2022.11.30_v1 p**– The first dataset generated from the semi-structured interviews with the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation conducted to identify their perceived barriers, opportunities, and incentives to be actively involved in collaborative governance schemes. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 30th of November 2022 (30/11/2022).
- **ROBIN_ToolboxAlphaTesting_Dataset2_2022.12.31_v2** – The second dataset created in the process of the Alpha testing of the ROBIN Toolbox, engaging stakeholders from the regional governance structures with a view to further fine-tuning its components. The last modification of this dataset, which in this case produced the second version of the dataset, was on the 31st of December 2023 (31/12/2023).

Versioning of information makes a revision of datasets uniquely identifiable and can be used to determine whether and how data changed over time and to define specifically which version the creators/editors are working with. Moreover, effective data versioning enables understanding if a newer version of a dataset is available and which are the changes between the different versions allowing for comparisons and preventing confusion. In this context, **a clear version number indicator is used in the naming convention** of every data file produced during ROBIN in order to facilitate the identification of different versions.

3.1.3 *Metadata allowing discovery*

In addition to consistent naming conventions and versioning, the project also follows a metadata-driven approach so as to allow discovery and further increase the searchability of the data, while also facilitating its understanding and re-use. Metadata is defined as “data about data” or “information

about information”¹¹. It is usually structured textual information that describes the creation, content, or context of a digital resource – be it a single file, part of a single file, or a collection of many files. Metadata is the glue which links information and data across the world wide web. It is the tool that helps people to discover, manage, describe, preserve and build relationships with and between digital resources ¹².

In particular, three distinct types of metadata exist¹³, as presented below:

- **Descriptive metadata**, used to identify and describe collections and related information resources. Descriptive metadata at the local level helps with searching and retrieving. In an online environment, descriptive metadata helps to discover resources. Most of the times includes information such as the title, author, date, description, identifier, etc.
- **Administrative metadata** is used to facilitate the management of information resources. It is helpful for both short-term and long-term management and processing of data. This is information that will not usually be relevant to the public but will be essential for staff to manage collections internally. Such metadata may be location information, acquisition information, etc.
- **Structural metadata** enables navigation and presentation of electronic resources. It documents how the components of an item are organized. Examples of structural metadata could be the way in which pages are ordered to form chapters of a book, a photograph that is included in a manuscript or a scrapbook or the JPEG and TIF files that were created from the original photograph negative, linked together.

With that in mind, **data produced/used during ROBIN is discoverable with metadata** suitable to its content and format. The project employs **metadata standards** to produce rich and consistent metadata with a view to supporting the long-term discovery, use and integrity of its data. More details on the metadata standards adopted by ROBIN are provided on the following subsection.

3.1.4 *Standards for metadata creation*

ROBIN employs standards for creating metadata for data collected/generated by the project, with a view to describing it with **rich metadata** and thus improving their discoverability and searchability. In result, effective searching, improved digital curation and easy sharing will be realized. In addition, the metadata standards applied enable the integration of metadata from a variety of sources into other technical systems.

With that in mind, for **ROBIN’s openly available data** the metadata standards provided by **Zenodo will be used**. Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is an open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE programme and operated by CERN. The repository along with its metadata standards have been adopted and are being used by numerous research communities, enabling them to deposit research papers, datasets, software, reports as well as other research outputs. Along these lines, Zenodo creates metadata to accompany the datasets that are uploaded to the repository, extending their reach to a wider audience of interested stakeholders. These metadata can be exported in several standard formats, including open and machine-readable ones (such as MARCXML, Dublin

¹¹ Huxley, L., & Jacobs, N. (2004). Online information services in the Social Sciences. Oxford: Chandos.

¹² Foulonneau, M., & Riley, J. (2008). Metadata for digital resources: Implementation, systems design and interoperability. Oxford: Chandos.

¹³ Caplan, P. (2003). Metadata fundamentals for all librarians. Chicago: American Library Association.

Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema), following the guidelines of OpenAIRE and are stored by Zenodo in JSON-format according to a defined JSON schema¹⁴.

Project **data not open, will also be annotated with open and machine-readable metadata** following the **Dublin Core Metadata standard**. The Dublin Core Metadata element set (certified with the ISO Standard 15836) is a standard which can be easily understood and implemented and as such, is one of the best-known metadata standards. It was originally developed as a core set of elements for describing the content of web pages and enabling their search and retrieval. Among the reasons for selecting this standard is also the fact that **Zenodo is compatible with Dublin Core metadata formats** and thus any initially closed data, that may become open at a later stage (e.g., due to a change in the consortium's policy), will not lose its metadata. With that said, the Dublin Core metadata standard is a simple yet effective set for creating rich metadata that will describe a wide range of resources. The fifteen element "Dublin Core" described in this standard is part of a larger set of metadata vocabularies and technical specifications maintained by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)¹⁵. The full set of vocabularies also includes sets of resource classes, vocabulary encoding schemes, and syntax encoding schemes. **An online metadata generator will be used** to produce the different metadata elements required (dublincoregenerator.com).

3.1.5 *Search keywords included in the metadata*

The project's data will be provided with search keywords with a view to optimizing its findability as well as its ultimate re-use by interested stakeholders during its entire lifetime. With that in mind, the metadata standards employed by ROBIN provide opportunities for tagging the data collected/generated and its content with keywords. In general, keywords are a subset of metadata and include words and phrases used to name data. In the context of ROBIN, keywords are used to add valuable information to the data collected/generated as well as to facilitate the description and interpretation of its content and value.

Along these lines, the project's strategy on keywords is underpinned by the following principles:

- The who, the what, the when, the where, and the why should be covered.
- Consistency among the different keyword tags needs to be ensured.
- Relevant, understandable and clear keywording ought to be sought.

In general, the keywords will comprise terms related to circular bioeconomy, governance models, and regional authorities. The keywords will accurately reflect the content of the datasets and avoid words used only once or twice within them.

3.1.6 *Offering metadata that can be harvested and indexed*

We know that the wild diversity of the metadata accompanying open data across the plethora of online repositories (e.g., disciplinary archives, institutional repositories, open access journals) can serve as barriers for their findability and sharing amongst different research communities. This is

¹⁴ For more information on the JSON format and the JSON schema visit the following website: <http://json-schema.org/>

¹⁵ Retrieved from: <https://www.dublincore.org/>

why in the context of ROBIN we have aligned our metadata creating approach with the **Open Archives Initiative (OAI)**, which promotes the use of a standard protocol for metadata harvesting, designed for better sharing and retrieval of data residing in distributed repositories. This protocol, namely the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)¹⁶ promotes interoperability standards that facilitate efficient dissemination of data amongst diverse communities¹⁷.

All structured **metadata linked to the project's open data will be offered in a way that can be exported and harvested** via the OAI-PMH thanks to the standards we adopt for metadata creation (see section 3.1.4). The same standards will also help us produce **metadata that facilitate indexing**. For instance, the use of the Dublin Core Metadata Standard (as further elaborated in section 3.3) provides a vocabulary of concepts with definitions in open-machine readable formats that enable easier indexing of metadata. Along these lines, there are several tools¹⁸ which implement the Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, such as **Arc source**, **EnhancedOAI Server** and **eprints.org**, and can be used for harvesting our data by different repositories.

ROBIN's openly available data will be uploaded in Zenodo, which is in line with FAIR principles, including the "To be Findable" principle. Metadata of each record uploaded in Zenodo is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Repository

The **data produced by ROBIN and deemed open for sharing and re-use, will be deposited to and securely stored by Zenodo (www.zenodo.org)**, which constitutes an open data repository and has been specifically selected to enable access to the project's open data free of charge. In fact, Zenodo builds and operates a simple service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions, among others, to share and showcase research results (including data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. It accepts any file format, promotes peer-reviewed openly accessible research, allows the creation of own collections and it is available free of charge both for ROBIN to upload and share data as well as for other stakeholders to explore, download and re-use these data.

Moreover, as a digital repository, Zenodo registers **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)** for all submitted data through DataCite¹⁹, which is the leading global non-profit organisation that provides PIDs (and specifically DOIs) for research data and preserves these submissions using the safe and trusted foundation of CERN's data centre, alongside the biggest scientific dataset in the world, the LHC's 100PB Big Data store²⁰. This means that the data preserved in Zenodo will be accessible for years to come, and the DOIs will function as perpetual links to the resources. DOIs remain valuable since

¹⁶ Retrieved from: <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

¹⁷ Corrado, E.M. (2005) 'The importance of open access, open source, and open standards for libraries', Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship.

¹⁸ For more information about the tools implementing the OAI-PMH: <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/tools/>

¹⁹ For more information on DataCite: <https://www.datacite.org/>

²⁰ Retrieved from: <https://www.software.ac.uk/tags/zenodo>

they are future-proofed against Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or even protocol changes, through resolvers (such as DOI²¹). With that in mind, an example of a DOI retrieved from this open repository follows the structure illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Typical DOI created by Zenodo

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3901783

3.2.2 Data

1. Openly available and closed data

ROBIN, in line with FAIR principles of data management in the context of Horizon Europe, adopts the good practice of making data as open as possible and as closed as necessary. This calls for partners to disseminate their data that have the potential to offer long-term value to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders that contributed to the collection/generation of these data, maximising the beneficial impact of ROBIN.

Only anonymised and aggregated data will be made open to ensure that data subjects cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from the project. The relevant project partner in each case will **undertake all the necessary anonymisation procedures** to anonymise the data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable (more details on data management responsibilities are provided in **Section 5.2**).

To this end, it is important to keep in mind that during the process of data anonymisation, data identifiers need to be removed, generalised, aggregated or distorted. Moreover, **anonymisation is different than pseudonymisation**, which falls under a distinct category in the GDPR - anonymisation theoretically destroys any way of identifying the data subject, while pseudonymisation allows for the data subject to be re-identified with additional information. Along these lines, the table which follows provides a **list of good practices** for the anonymisation of quantitative and qualitative data derived from the tour guide on data management of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

Table 4: Good practices for data anonymisation

Type of data	Good practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remove or aggregate variables or reduce the precision or detailed textual meaning of a variable. Aggregate or reduce the precision of a variable such as age or place of residence. As a general rule, report the lowest level of geo-referencing that will not potentially breach respondent confidentiality. Generalise the meaning of a detailed text variable by replacing potentially disclosive free-text responses with more general text.

²¹ Retrieved from: <http://dx.doi.org/>

Type of data	Good practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restrict the upper or lower ranges of a continuous variable to hide outliers if the values for certain individuals are unusual or atypical within the wider group researched.
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use pseudonyms or generic descriptors to edit identifying information, rather than blanking-out that information. Plan anonymisation at the time of transcription or initial write-up, (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews need special attention for harmonised editing). Use pseudonyms or replacements that are consistent within the research team and throughout the project. For example, using the same pseudonyms in publications and follow-up research. Use 'search and replace' techniques carefully so that unintended changes are not made, and misspelt words are not missed. Identify replacements in text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg>word to be anonymised</seg>. Create an anonymisation log (also known as a de-anonymisation key) of all replacements, aggregations or removals made and store such a log securely and separately from the anonymised data files.

Source: Tour guide on data management of the CESSDA²²

With that in mind, the following table presents the data collected/generated during the course of the project that will be made openly available. In case certain data cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), a justification for that choice is provided.

Table 5: Data availability

No	Data	Availability	Notes
1	Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	Open & Closed	For MARC members who will give written consent to publish their profiles (e.g., full name, photo, short bio) on the website, the data will become open. For MARC members who will not give consent their data will be closed and managed internally among the ROBIN partners. Data availability will be further elaborated in D6.3, according to each MARC member's written consent.
2	Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional	Open	To be available in D1.3 "Circular Bioeconomy Governance profiles of

²² Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation>

No	Data	Availability	Notes
	Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance		ROBIN regions” (Public). The raw data collected in order to generate the results of this activity will not be publicly available.
3	Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions	Open	-
4	Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy	Open	It is envisaged that data underpinning the good practices collection and analysis may be made available in a pseudonymised format. Some of the data may be aggregated in the deliverable report.
5	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Open	-
6	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Open	-
7	Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region	Open	Public deliverable D2.2.
8	Development of the ROBIN Tools	Open	It is envisaged that data underpinning the good practices collection and analysis may be made available in a pseudonymized format. Some of the data may be aggregated in the deliverable report.
9	ROBIN knowledge platform	Open	(Deliverables are public)
10	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas	Open	(Deliverables are public)
11	Policy Monitoring System tool	Open	(Deliverables are public)
12	Environmental Protection Planning tool	Open	(Deliverables are public)
13	ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio	Open	(Deliverables are public)
14	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	Open & Closed	Open: Toolbox validation plans in D3.1. Closed: Roadmaps or other policies to be put under testing, if they are still not published and personal contact details.

No	Data	Availability	Notes
15	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Open & Closed	Open: Opinions of the Alpha and Beta testing should be anonymised in case disclosed in D3.2. Closed: Personal contact details related to project regions (Alpha) as well as external pilot regions (Beta) participating in the testing. Contact details of participants in the two support action events.
16	Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox	Open	Public deliverable D3.2
17	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Open	N/A
18	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Open	-
19	Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations	Open	N/A
20	Website and social media analytics	Open & Closed	Website and social media analytics will be available only to ROBIN consortium and the EU Commission. In case statistics are shared, data will be aggregated and anonymised before being made openly available, while personal data will be treated as expected by the GDPR.
21	Data collected from project events	Open & Closed	Data collected from project events will be available only to ROBIN consortium and the EU Commission. In case there is a need to share information for dissemination and communication purposes, any personal information will be anonymised before being made openly available.
22	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions	Open & Closed	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions will be available only to ROBIN consortium and the EU Commission. In case there is a need to share information for dissemination and communication purposes, any personal information will be

No	Data	Availability	Notes
			anonymised before being made openly available.
23	Newsletter subscriptions	Closed	Data from newsletter subscriptions will remain closed as it contains personal information and is useful only for internal reporting purposes.
24	Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	Open & Closed	Information about the candidate members will remain confidential between the consortium and personal data will be treated as expected by the GDPR. The final composition of the AB together with the terms of reference will be reported in a public deliverable (D5.3)
25	Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives	Open	-

It is important to note that **all personal data collected / generated will be considered as closed data prior to their anonymisation and aggregation** to safeguard the confidentiality of the data subjects.

2. Data accessibility and availability

Public access to the open data will be made available and free of charge through Zenodo, which will automatically link to OpenAIRE. The data will be fully accessible thanks to the included metadata and the search facility available on Zenodo. At the same time, closed data are intended to be stored and shared amongst authorised members of the consortium through cloud storage and file sharing providers which constitute structures that maintain and manage data and make these data accessible over a network, usually the internet (i.e., Google Drive). Before starting using these cloud services from providers situated both inside and outside the EEA, we have ensured that they comply with the relevant GDPR requirements.

The following table presents where data will be made accessible in the context of ROBIN.

Table 6: Data accessibility

No	Data	Notes
1	Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	ROBIN website (for the MARC members that give written consent)
2	Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional	Zenodo repository

No	Data	Notes
	Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance	
3	Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions	ROBIN website, Zenodo, Openair, AUTH's website (i.e., Laboratory of Geoinformatics website)
4	Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy	It is envisaged that pseudonymized data underpinning the collection of good practices may be made available through Zenodo.
5	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	ROBIN website, Zenodo, Openair, AUTH's website (i.e., Laboratory of Geoinformatics website)
6	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Paper published in open access and Zenodo
7	Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region	ROBIN website, Zenodo
8	Development of the ROBIN Tools	It is envisaged that pseudonymized data underpinning the development of tools may be made available through Zenodo.
9	ROBIN knowledge platform	ROBIN Toolbox (Public deliverable)
10	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas	ROBIN Toolbox (Public deliverable)
11	Policy Monitoring System tool	ROBIN Toolbox (Public deliverable)
12	Environmental Protection Planning tool	ROBIN Toolbox (Public deliverable)
13	ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio	ROBIN Toolbox (Public deliverable)
14	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	ROBIN website (D3.1) and Zenodo
15	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	ROBIN website (D3.2) and Zenodo
16	Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox	Public deliverable D3.2, ROBIN Toolbox, Zenodo
17	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Zenodo, ROBIN website
18	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Zenodo
19	Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations	Zenodo, ROBIN website

No	Data	Notes
20	Website and social media analytics	ROBIN website
21	Data collected from project events	ROBIN website
22	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions	ROBIN website
23	Newsletter subscriptions	N/A (closed data)
24	Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	ROBIN website
25	Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives	ROBIN website and the websites of the collaborative projects and initiatives

3. Restrictions on use

By utilising Zenodo for sharing the project's openly available data, ROBIN can apply **different levels of accessibility** for these data taking into account any relevant issues (such as ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related, etc.).

More specifically, **Zenodo offers the following levels of data accessibility:**

- **Open access:** Data remains available for re-use. Nevertheless, the level in which these data can be re-used is determined also by their accompanied licence for re-use (see subsection 3.4.3).
- **Embargoed status:** Access to the data will be restricted until the end of the embargo period, at which time, the content will automatically become publicly available.
- **Restricted access:** The data will not be made publicly available and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of the project partner that have the responsibility of the data.
- **Closed access:** The data are protected against unauthorized access at all levels and only members of the consortium have the right to access it.

Project partners will mainly use the open access level to disseminate the project's data amongst the interested stakeholders. Data that will not be available for re-use will be accessible only by authorised partners of ROBIN's consortium and /or authorised personnel from the funding authority of the project.

Moreover, **ROBIN will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications** that may be produced in the framework of the project. In particular, according to the Grant Agreement, ROBIN will:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the

licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and

- information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

4. Identity ascertainment and data access committee

The identity of stakeholders who want to access the data on Zenodo is not necessary to be ascertained, as the uploaded on Zenodo data are publicly open and no authorization is needed. On the other hand, closed for the public data will be available only to authorized consortium partners through dedicated mechanisms provided by the cloud storage service employed by the respective partners in order to deposit the data. As further elaborated in Section 6 of this DMP, technical access controls are built into the ROBIN website and will be built into its toolbox²³ as well, in order to ascertain the identity and access rights of those who want to access the data.

The need for a data access committee to evaluate or approve access requests to personal data, is not foreseen because only authorized partners will have access to the project's closed data, accessible only by using their credentials (username/password), and no third-party will re-use them for their benefit.

3.2.3 Metadata

1. Availability and licences

Metadata of deposited publications generated in the context of ROBIN will be **open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0)** or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles for data management adopted by the project (in particular machine-actionable). Such **metadata will provide information, at least, about the following:**

- The publication at hand (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue);
- Reference to the Horizon Europe funding;
- The name of the project, including its acronym and Grant Agreement number;
- Any particular licensing terms which may apply (depending on the chosen license);
- Persistent identifiers that have been attributed to the publication;
- Authors involved in the action, their organisations and the project itself.

Where applicable, the metadata will also include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication. The metadata will be available through Zenodo. It is quite unlikely that Zenodo will terminate its operation and stop providing its services, but in such a case all data, metadata, code and documentation uploaded will be transferred and hosted to other suitable repositories without undue delay. In this respect, it is

²³ More information on the toolbox's access control will be provided in the interim version of the DMP.

important to note that, since all of ROBIN's openly available data will make use of PIDs (i.e., DOIs), which is further elaborated in subsection 3.1.1, the links to the data will not be affected. In parallel, the project's data that will not be openly available for sharing will be deposited, together with their accompanying metadata, code and documentation (if necessary), to the cloud web storage service employed by the project.

2. Methods, Software tools and documentation to access the data

ROBIN emphasises the accessibility of the data collected / generated during the project. With that in mind, no specialised method, software tool and / or documentation is expected to be needed at the moment, in order to access the data. Stakeholders will have the ability to access the data by simply using their web browser (e.g., Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, etc.) through their computers (either desktop or laptop), smartphones and/or tablets.

More specifically, they first need to access Zenodo through its webpage (following the link <https://zenodo.org/>) and utilise the search engine of the repository to search for interesting data. By typing the name of the project (or any other relevant keyword connected to the ROBIN data) the search engine will direct the user to the project's data, ready to be explored and re-used. Moreover, since the data will be available in open formats, we will be ensuring that they can appropriately be read by a range of different software that are widely and freely accessible to all potential users of the data.

Closed data will only be accessed by authorised project partners through the usage of a cloud storage service. Again, no specialised method, software tool and / or documentation is needed to this end.

As it was further elaborated in subsection 3.2.1, if Zenodo terminates its operation and stops providing its services, in such a case all data, metadata, code and documentation uploaded will be transferred and hosted to other suitable repositories without undue delay.

Along these lines, this section has provided the methodology applied in the frame of ROBIN to ensure that its data are as openly accessible as possible by any stakeholder that may find them interesting for re-use. In this context, ROBIN also focuses on providing metadata standards and appropriate metadata vocabularies to increase data interoperability. The following section provides further details in this respect.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability refers to the ability of systems and services that create, exchange and use data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data²⁴. With that in mind, ROBIN has adopted in its data management methodology the use of metadata vocabularies, standards and methods that will increase the interoperability of the data collected/generated through its activities.

More specifically, **the interoperability of the data that will not be publicly shared will be facilitated by the use of the Dublin Core Metadata standard.** This standard is a small “metadata

²⁴ L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives

element set” which accounts for issues that must be resolved in order to ensure that data meet traditional standards for quality and consistency, while remaining broadly interoperable with other data sources in the linked data environment. The fifteen elements of the standard provide a vocabulary of concepts with natural-language definitions (e.g., title, creator, author, etc.) that are instantly converted into open machine-readable formats (such as XML, HTML, etc.), enabling machine-processability. Each element is optional and may be repeated, while the standard itself offers ways exist for refining them, encouraging the use of encoding and vocabulary schemes. The vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard is presented in the following table²⁵:

Table 7: Dublin Core Metadata standard vocabulary

No	Element	Element definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.
3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.
12	Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
13	Relation	A reference to a related resource.
14	Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource.
15	Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.

Along similar lines, **the interoperability of openly available data will be facilitated through Zenodo**, which adopts community- endorsed practices, since its metadata are stored internally in JSON format according to a defined JSON schema. This encloses HTML microdata that allows machine-readable data to be embedded in HTML documents in the form of nested groups of name-

²⁵ Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

value pairs. Moreover, the JSON schema provides a collection of shared vocabularies in microdata format that can be used to mark-up pages in ways that can be understood by major search engines.

ROBIN's data will offer qualified references to other data. A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. Our goal is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data, balanced against the time/energy involved in making a good data model. To be more concrete, our references will specify if one dataset builds on another data set, if additional datasets are needed to complete the data, or if complementary information is stored in a different dataset. The links between the datasets will also be described and, all datasets will be properly cited, including their persistent identifiers.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 *Documentation for validating data analysis and facilitating data re-use*

By utilising Zenodo for sharing the project's openly available data, ROBIN ensures the facilitation of data access, validation and re-use, in compliance to the general policies of Zenodo regarding content, access and reuse. More specifically, the following principles are followed by Zenodo to make data re-useable according to the FAIR principles²⁶:

- R1: (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.

- R1.1: (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, and is referring to an Open Definition license. Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.

- R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user. Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.

- R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.

3.4.2 *License schemes to permit the widest use possible*

Data will be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible. Moreover, the application of a licence to ROBIN's open data is a simple way to ensure that any interested third-party can re-use it. In this context, licences are the instrument which permit a third-

²⁶ Retrieved from: <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

party to copy, distribute, display and/or modify the project's data only for the purposes that are set by the licence. Licences typically grant permissions on condition that certain terms are met. While the precise details vary, three conditions are commonly found in licences which are the attribution, non-derivative, and non-commerciality.

Along these lines, ROBIN publishes openly available data under the **Creative Commons licencing scheme** to foster their re-use and build an equitable and accessible environment for them. Zenodo provides ROBIN the **opportunity to publish its open data under five Creative Common licences** as follows:

- **Creative commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0)** according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, must be distributed under the same license as the original. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)** according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- **Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-ND 4.0)** during which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- **Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)** based on which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get a permission by project partners first. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- **Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0)** according to which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get a permission by project partners first. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 2: CC BY-SA 4.0

Figure 3: CC BY 4.0

Figure 4: CC BY-ND 4.0

Figure 5: CC BY-NC 4.0

Figure 6: CC BY-NC-ND 4.0

Different licensing schemes may be selected to better fit the need of ROBIN's open data ensuring not only their long-term preservation and re-use but also the interests of the consortium along with the rights of individuals for whom the data are about. In such a case, this subsection of the DMP will be updated accordingly.

3.4.3 Availability for re-use

The re-use of data is a key component of ROBIN’s methodology for making data FAIR. In fact, making data available for re-use ensures interested stakeholders, other than project partners, can benefit from these data, contributing towards maximising the impact of the project. **Rich metadata** created based on metadata standards that enable proper discovery as well as **appropriate licensing schemes facilitate the re-use of ROBIN’s open data**, allowing them to find valuable utility even after the end of ROBIN project.

In principle, it is expected that data will become available for re-use no later than 120 days after the end of its processing in the framework of the project (i.e., collection, anonymisation, aggregation, etc.) to ensure that any additional data management activities required to this end do not compete with the timely delivery of the project’s planned outputs.

With that in mind, the expected time that ROBIN’s data will be made openly accessible and uploaded to Zenodo is indicatively provided in the following table:

Table 8: Expected time that data will be made open through Zenodo²⁷

No	Data	Expected time for making data open	Notes
1	Set up of ROBIN’s Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	N/A	Data will be open in ROBIN website only for MARC members that give written consent (28/02/2023)
2	Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance	20/03/2023	Data will be open in Zenodo repository
3	Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions	March 2024 (M19)	Upon approval by the EC (Review meeting)
4	Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy	01/03/2023	It is envisaged this may be made available following completion of the report. However, should we plan to publish the results/data in peer review this may be delayed.
5	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	March 2024 (M19)	Upon approval by the EC (Review meeting)
6	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	30/01/2024	-

²⁷ This timetable is based on expectations and may be modified during the course of the project taking into account any unforeseen risk that may occur.

No	Data	Expected time for making data open	Notes
7	Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region	30/01/2024	-
8	Development of the ROBIN Tools	31/12/2023	It is envisaged this may be made available following completion of the deliverable report. However, should we plan to publish the results/data in peer review this may be delayed.
9	ROBIN knowledge platform	30/04/2025	M32
10	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas	30/04/2025	M32
11	Policy Monitoring System tool	30/04/2025	M32
12	Environmental Protection Planning tool	30/04/2025	M32
13	ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio	30/04/2025	M32
14	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	28/06/2024	But only for open data. See notes in table 5.
15	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	28/06/2025	But only for open data. See notes in table 5.
16	Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox	30/04/2025	M32
17	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	31/08/2025	-
18	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	31/08/2025	-
19	Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations	31/08/2025	-
20	Website and social media analytics	N/A	Website and social media analytics will be available only to ROBIN consortium and the EU Commission. In case statistics are shared, data will be aggregated and anonymised before being made openly available, while

No	Data	Expected time for making data open	Notes
			personal data will be treated as expected by the GDPR.
21	Data collected from project events	N/A	Data collected from project events will be available only to ROBIN consortium and the EU Commission. In case there is a need to share information for dissemination and communication purposes, any personal information will be anonymised before being made openly available.
22	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions	N/A	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions will be available only to ROBIN consortium and the EU Commission. In case there is a need to share information for dissemination and communication purposes, any personal information will be anonymised before being made openly available.
23	Newsletter subscriptions	N/A	Newsletter subscriptions are closed data
24	Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	N/A	Data will be open in ROBIN website (28/02/2022)
25	Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives	M1 to M36	-

3.4.4 Data provenance

Data provenance is the documentation of where a piece of data comes from and the processes and methodology by which it was produced. Put simply, provenance answers the questions of why and how the data was produced, as well as where, when and by whom²⁸. Accurately recording data provenance is a cornerstone of good data management. ROBIN will use specific elements of the

²⁸ <https://ardc.edu.au/resource/data-provenance/>

Dublin Core Metadata Standards²⁹ and the **W3C Provenance Data Model**³⁰, to generate specific text files (e.g., README) that will accurately capture the history of each data entity throughout its versions (e.g., based on the DOI versioning Zenodo provides)³¹.

3.4.5 *Data quality assurance processes*

Quality Assurance (QA) and **Quality Control (QC)** activities are an integral part of ROBIN's data management methodology and are implemented prior to the publication of any data to Zenodo, safeguarding the transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness and accuracy of the data.

QA is a planned system of review procedures conducted outside the framework of developing a dataset, by personnel not directly involved in the dataset development process³². In the context of ROBIN, it takes the form of **peer-reviews of methods and/or data summaries** to assess the quality of the dataset and identify any need for improvement, ensuring that the dataset correctly incorporates the scientific knowledge and data generated.

QC is defined as a system of checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset being compiled³³. The relevant procedures of ROBIN are designed to provide routine technical checks as they measure and control data consistency, integrity, correctness and completeness as well as identify and address errors and omissions. In this context, QC checks cover everything from data acquisition and handling, application of approved procedures and methods, and documentation. Some of the general quality checks undertaken in the framework of the project include checking (i) for transcription errors in data input; (ii) that scale measures are within the range of acceptable values; and (iii) whether proper naming conventions are used.

²⁹ https://www.dublincore.org/resources/userguide/creating_metadata/#Provenance

³⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

³¹ <https://help.zenodo.org/>

³² 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

³³ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

4. Other research outputs

At the moment of elaborating the initial version of ROBIN's Data Management Plan, no other research outputs have been identified and are expected to be generated or re-used in the context of the project.

5. Allocation of resources

5.1 Estimated costs for making data FAIR

The costs required for making the data collected/generated during ROBIN's activities FAIR are integrated into the budget of the project. With that in mind, the table which follows provides an overview of the estimated costs of making data FAIR as well as their budget source within the framework of ROBIN.

Table 9: Estimated costs for making data FAIR

No	Data Processing / Management Activity	Budget source	Total estimated effort in Person Months ³⁴	Total estimated cost in Euro ³⁵
1	Collection	Budget allocated to the WP under which the respective data are processed	24.66	126,682.67 €
2	Documentation	Budget allocated to the WP under which the respective data are processed	6.16	31,670.67 €
3	Storage	Budget allocated to the WP under which the respective data are processed	3.08	15,835.33 €
4	Access and security	Budget allocated to the WP under which the respective data are processed	3.08	15,835.33 €
5	Preservation	Budget allocated to the WP under which the respective data are processed	1.54	7,917.67 €
6	Availability and re-use	Budget allocated to the WP under which the respective data are processed	9.25	47,506.00 €
7	Overall data management	WP6	3.95	20,293.95 €
			Total	265,741.61 €

In order to produce the estimations of the costs for making data FAIR in the context of ROBIN, a series of **assumptions** were made, taking into account the respective **guidelines** provided by the

³⁴ The total estimated effort for each data processing / management activity reflects the cumulative effort for the implementation of the respective activity for all data collected / generated across the different WPs of ROBIN.

³⁵ The total cost of each data processing / management activity is calculated by multiplying the effort estimated for the respective activity with the weighted average cost of a person month in the framework of ROBIN.

Research Data Management Support, a multidisciplinary network of data experts within Utrecht University³⁶, as well as of the UK Data Service and its data management costing tool³⁷. With that in mind, the estimated costs for making ROBIN's data FAIR cover **data-related activities and resources across the data lifecycle**, spanning from collection and documentation through storage and preservation over to sharing and re-use.

In particular, costs for **data collection** cover activities necessary for acquiring external datasets (if required), gathering/generating new data, transcribing (if applicable), formatting and organising these data as well as acquiring informed consent from data subjects. These data processing activity reflects the majority of the costs required for making data FAIR as the majority of ROBIN's data constitutes new data collected/generated over the course of the project. At the same time, **data documentation** costs address the effort required for describing data (e.g., marking data with variable and value labels, code descriptions, etc.) as well as creating well-defined metadata along with a meaningful description of the context and methodology of how data was collected/generated and processed (where necessary).

Costs for **data storage** include the resources required for ensuring adequate storage space for the data as well as the effort necessary for conducting data back-ups, while **data access and security** costs encompass costs related to ensuring access to the data as well as for protecting it from unauthorised access or use or from disclosure. Given that the storage of ROBIN's data will not require the procurement of additional space (other than what is already available to project partners) as well as that no special measures or software are required to access and secure the data (other than what is inherently built in to the repositories of ROBIN's data), such costs are kept to a minimum.

Data preservation costs, on the other hand, are estimated relatively higher than data storage, access and security costs, as additional effort will be required in several cases in order to convert the collected/generated data from their original form (e.g., physical interview transcripts) to an open and/or machine-readable format suitable for long-term preservation (e.g., to an .xlsx format.). Adequate effort for **data availability and re-use** costs is also foreseen to safeguard the appropriate digitisation and anonymisation of the data as well as cover any resources required for data sharing and cleaning. Along the same lines, appropriate effort is foreseen for **overall data management** as well, in order to cover the effort related with the operationalisation of data management in the framework of ROBIN.

Finally, costs for **long-term preservation** in the framework of ROBIN are assumed to be negligible, since the open data of the project will be hosted in the repository of Zenodo free of charge.

5.2 Data management responsibilities

For the effective, proper and secure handling of the data collected/generated in the frame of ROBIN, specific data management roles have been established within the data management methodology and procedures of the project. These responsibilities are outlined in this section of the DMP and are as follows.

³⁶ Research Data Management Support. Guides: Costs of data management. Utrecht University. Retrieved from: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/guides/costs-of-data-management>

³⁷ UK Data Service. Costing Data Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/plan/costing>

Project Coordinator (PC): The PC, QPL, is responsible for overall data management in the framework of ROBIN, including the elaboration of the DMP and its updates (when necessary along with support of all partners). At the same time, the PC is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form to be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant activities of the project as well as for drafting the project's Privacy Policy that has been uploaded on the project's website. The PC in collaboration with the relevant project partners (e.g., Task Leaders) will examine if additional specific privacy policies are required for certain project's tasks and will coordinate the elaboration of such privacy policies. Finally, the PC coordinates with Work Package Leaders, Task Leaders and Responsible Partners to determine whether and how the data collected / generated or re-used by the project are shared and become available for re-use, contributes to its quality assurance and uploads the project's openly available data to Zenodo.

Work Package Leaders (WPL): The WPL is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. Moreover, they align with the PC and the respective Work Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. This includes the definition of access procedures as well as potential embargo periods along with any necessary software and/or other tools which may be required for data sharing and re-use. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Work Task Leaders.

Work Task Leaders (WTL): WTLs are responsible for the data collected / generated or re-used in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership as well as for safeguarding their appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the Informed Consent Form and Data Subject Request Form templates, to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. WTLs are responsible for identifying the need for a specific privacy policy regarding the task they are leading and collaborate with the PC for drafting and releasing it to the public. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data collected / generated or re-used through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium or openly (including the use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymisation techniques, creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.).

Partners: All project partners are tasked to collect, digitise, anonymise, store, destroy and / or otherwise process data for the specific purpose of the activity in which it has been collected / generated or re-used within the project. They are responsible for appropriately collecting the necessary consent for processing data as well as for ensuring that the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form used to this end are properly adjusted to the needs of the activity they are participating (including references to the project's Privacy Policy and any other applicable specific privacy policies) and, in any particularities, applicable to their organisation while ensuring adherence to provisions of relevant national data protection legislation in their respective country. Moreover, they are responsible for managing the consents they have collected with a view to demonstrating their compliance with the relevant applicable EU and national regulation(s). Finally, they perform quality checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset(s) held within their records.

Data repositories: Data repositories are tasked with the storage and long-term preservation of the project's data. In this respect, Zenodo will maintain and preserve the openly available data of ROBIN, enabling its sharing and re-use. To this end, Zenodo assigns metadata and DOIs to the data, while also taking all necessary measures to securely back-up the data and restore it, safeguarding its long-term preservation.

In this context, the following table illustrates the allocation of data management responsibilities amongst the members of the ROBIN consortium per data collected/generated or re-used under each WP.

Table 10: Data management responsibilities of ROBIN's partners per data collected/generated under each WP

WP	WPL	Data	Tasks	WTL	Responsible Partners
WP1	AUTH	Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	Task 1.1	WR	All
		Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance	Task 1.1	WR	All
		Development of a Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models in European Regions	Task 1.2	AUTH	All
		Identification of good practices and analysis of case studies of supporting local operators and innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy	Task 1.3	MTU	All
		Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Task 1.4	AUTH	All
WP2	CTA	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Task 2.1	CTA	All
		Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region	Task 2.2	CTA	All
		Development of the ROBIN Tools	Task 2.3	MTU	QPL, CTA, WR, PED, S2I, ZSK, AUTH and RCM
		Data collected/generated by the utilisation of the ROBIN Toolbox	Task 2.4	S2I	QPL, CTA, WR, PED, ZSK, MTU, AUTH and RCM
WP3	BPRO	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	Task 3.1	BPRO	All
		Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Task 3.2	BPRO	All
		Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox	Task 3.3	S2I	All

WP	WPL	Data	Tasks	WTL	Responsible Partners
WP4	PED	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Task 4.1	PED	QPL, CTA, WR, S2I, ZSK, MTU, AUTH, RCM, IFA, BPRO and SRA
		Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Task 4.2	CTA	All
		Development of the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations	Task 4.3	PED	QPL, CTA, WR, S2I, ZSK, MTU, AUTH, RCM, IFA, BPRO and SRA
WP5	WR	Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities	Task 5.1	WR	All
		Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	Task 5.2	WR	All
		Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives	Task 5.3	S2I	All

6. Data security

ROBIN will securely handle any collected / generated or re-used data throughout its entire lifecycle as it is essential to safeguard these data against accidental loss and / or unauthorised access. To achieve this the project will apply appropriate technical and organisational measures based on a risk assessment of the relevant data that takes into account the impact and the likelihood of a potential data breach. With that in mind, the project's data security strategy aims at minimizing the probability that a data breach will occur during the course and after the completion of ROBIN, resulting either from human error or hardware failure, as well as inhibit any unauthorised access. Particularly, in case of personal data collection / generation it is crucial that these **data can only be accessible by those authorised to do so**.

All project partners are responsible for processing³⁸ data using appropriate means, such as private servers or cloud service providers that adhere to the relevant legal data protection requirements (e.g., GDPR) and will ensure that this **data is protected**, and any **necessary data security controls have been implemented**, to minimize the risk of information leak and destruction. This case refers to the data that will be closed and therefore will not be shared and / or re-used within the framework of the project. In this case, to minimize the consequences of potential data losses, the data will be **backed up at regular time intervals based on change frequency and criticality. The backed-up files will be stored in appropriate storage media including external hard drives, flash drives, NAS devices and reputable cloud services**, so as to safeguard their preservation, while also enabling their recovery at any time. Moreover, **integrity checks**³⁹ will be carried out regularly ensuring that the stored data has not been changed or corrupted.

Access to closed data will only be permitted to authorised project partners. In case there is a **personal data breach**, the responsible **project partner will notify, without undue delay** and, where feasible, no later than **72 hours after having become aware of it, its competent national supervisory authority** (e.g., data protection authority) **as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach**. Moreover, the responsible partner will document any personal data breaches, including information such as the facts relevant to the breach, its effects and the remedial action(s) taken.

Identification and authentication access controls play an important role in the context of the project, as they help partners to protect the data collected / generated or re-used during ROBIN and especially personal data. To this end, each project partner is responsible for and committed to ensuring the application of appropriate access controls to the data they are processing. At the same time, **technical access controls are built into the ROBIN website through dedicated username**

³⁸ Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation), means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

³⁹ An integrity check is the process of comparing the current state of stored data and/or programs to a previously recorded state in order to detect any changes.

and password for Wordpress platform that are managed exclusively by WR and will be built into the ROBIN toolbox⁴⁰ as well, setting out clear roles with access rights to the data stored there, so that only authorised personnel have access. Each project partner will be provided with unique accounts containing one or more roles assigned to them and at the same time enforcing role-based security when its staff processes the project's data. These accounts are expected to be username / password protected, maximising access control. Finally, in order to safeguard the privacy of the users of the ROBIN website and the ROBIN toolbox, dedicated **privacy policies** will define the way in which these online spaces collect, process and use personal data, the security procedures followed, the users' rights as well as the cookies policy employed.

On another note, openly available data will be stored safely for long-term preservation on Zenodo, in the same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN's Large Hadron Collider, using CERN's battle-tested repository software INVENIO, which is used by some of the world's largest repositories (such as INSPIRE HEP and the CERN Document Server). Along these lines, data is stored and backed-up in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Both data files and metadata are kept in multiple online replicas and independent replicas ensuring their long-term preservation as well as their recovery when necessary. Moreover, for each file two independent MD5 checksums are stored. One checksum is stored by INVENIO, used to detect changes to files made from outside of it whereas the other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks. In this context, access control is applied by the different level of openness that Zenodo allows (i.e., open, restricted and closed).

⁴⁰ The partner responsible for creating the digital form of the toolbox (AUP) considered that it is too early at this point to provide a more detailed description of its technical access controls. More information will be provided in the interim version of the DMP.

7. Ethics and other issues

This Chapter addresses the ethical aspects of the ROBIN's Data Management Plan and the ethical compliance of the underlying data foreseen to be collected / generated or re-used under the project's activities. The project will process data that is not included in any special category of personal data (i.e., non-sensitive data) according to the relevant data protection legislation (e.g., GDPR). In accordance with the **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (GDPR)**, all personal data processed for project's activities shall be:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject;
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes relative to project's objectives and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed;
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data (see section 6).

For all personal data processing activities within the framework of the project at least one lawful basis as of Art. 6 GDPR applies. Where informed consent is chosen as the lawful basis for processing, all relevant provisions of the data protection legislation (e.g., Art.7 GDPR) are observed. Under this light, further details about the **scope of the activities that entail data collection/generation or re-use** in the frame of ROBIN along with the procedures for identifying/recruiting suitable stakeholders to take part in them as well as for obtaining their informed consent are defined by the respective WP Leaders (AUTH for WP1, CTA for WP2, BPRO for WP3, PED for WP4, WR for WP5, QPL for WP6). Moreover, **personal data processing carried out by partners are in line with relevant EU and national regulations**. The project's Privacy Policy and the templates of the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form, used in the implementation of the project's activities, are compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation and annexed to this DMP (see Annex). Last but not least, **no transfer of personal data outside the EU is foreseen as part of the project's implementation**. In case of data storage providers situated both inside and outside the EEA, partners are committed to ensure their compliance with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

It is important to highlight that **each partner is responsible for ensuring that the templates for the Informed Consent Form and Subject Data Request Form (including references to the project's Privacy Policy and any other applicable specific privacy policies) are appropriately adjusted** according to (i) the needs of the activity for which they are being used by them as well as to (ii) the relevant data protection laws and regulations applicable to their respective countries and / or organisation. **All partners should keep records to demonstrate that data subjects have consented to the processing of their personal data** and use consent management mechanisms that make it easy for individuals to withdraw their consent.

Finally, regarding **other national/funder/sectoral/departmental procedures for data management** in the framework of ROBIN the following can be included:

- **AUTH:** According to the *Regulation of Principles and Operation of the Research Ethics Committee of AUTH*, every research proposal or project, before its implementation, has to be approved by the Research Ethics Committee. In the case of ROBIN and according to the decision No 151204/2022, when AUTH performs data collection including the participation of individuals, the survey (i.e., questionnaires, data collection form etc) along with the informed consent form have to be submitted to the Research Ethics Committee for review and approval before its implementation.

At the moment of drafting this deliverable, apart from the aforementioned, **no other national/funder/sectoral/departmental procedures for data management were used in the framework of ROBIN.**

8. Conclusions and way forward

This initial version of the ROBIN DMP aims at safeguarding the sound management of the data collected, processed and/or generated during the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them FAIR. It describes all the underlying processes of the ROBIN data management, collection, process and generation, in accordance with the GDPR guidelines, and sheds light on (i) the data being collected, processed, generated and/or re-used under the project activities, (ii) the specific objectives under which each dataset is collected, processed, generated and/or re-used, (iii) the management of the other research outputs of the project (iv) the allocation of resources and data management responsibilities and (v) the data security and ethical aspects of the data.

In the framework of ROBIN, the DMP is a living document and is updated throughout the course of the project, considering its latest developments and available results. It is expected to be further developed and updated at least twice by the end the project (i.e., as D6.3 by M18 and as D6.4 by M36). If necessary, additional ad hoc updates may be released in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect modifications in the methodologies applied or other aspects relevant to data management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors.

9. Annexes

9.1 Annex I – Privacy Policy

PRIVACY POLICY

1. Who we are:

ROBIN is a project funded by the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon Europe. ROBIN sets out to empower Europe's regional authorities (in 5 European Regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece) to fulfil their role as agents of just, inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. The project provides support to co-shape their governance structures and models in ways that accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. To this end, it sets-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key quadruple helix stakeholders to co-create and work alongside novel governance structures, mandated to coordinate and execute circular bioeconomy strategies in coordination with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiatives Coordination and Support Office. The project provides them with tailored support for enhanced and more inclusive stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the design, operation and monitoring of their governance models.

The partners of the ROBIN consortium, listed below, process certain types of personal data for the purposes of the project. Each partner is responsible for the personal data they collect and process during their activities under the framework of the project:

- Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC, Greece (Coordinator), <https://qplan-intl.gr/>
- FUNDACION CORPORACION TECNOLOGICA DE ANDALUCIA, Spain, <http://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/en/>
- WHITE RESEARCH SPRL, Belgium, www.white-research.eu
- PEDAL CONSULTING SRO, Slovakia, www.pedal-consulting.eu
- STEINBEIS 2I GMBH, Germany, steinbeis-europa.de
- ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO, Slovakia, <https://razsk.sk/>
- MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, Ireland, www.circbio.ie
- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, Greece, www.auth.gr
- REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA, Greece, www.pkm.gov.gr
- CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL, Spain, <https://juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturapescaaguaydesarrollorural.html>

- INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIONY FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA, Spain, <https://ifapa.junta-andalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/ifapa/web/>
- BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTEMBERG GMBH, Germany, www.bio-pro.de
- SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY, Ireland, www.southernassembly.ie

For further information, we can be contacted at: info@robin-project.eu

2. How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

Directly. We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual subscribes to our newsletter/s;
- an individual registers to attend meetings and events we host and during attendance at such events;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organized by us.

Indirectly. We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g., LinkedIn).

3. What types of data we collect?

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- **contact details** (name/ surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number);
- **professional information** (job title, organization, field of expertise);
- **demographics** (e.g., age, gender, nationality);
- **information about what a person knows or believes.**
- **videos and photos** (from people that attend our events).

4. Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

Legal obligations - for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.

Consent – for processing activities such as organization of surveys and interviews, completing of questionnaires and dissemination of project's results.

Contractual obligations - for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

5. What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, surveys);
- Dissemination our project's results to different types of stakeholder;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

6. How we secure your personal data when we process it

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organizational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organizations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Some of our partners have appointed a Data Protection Officer.

7. Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint, Google);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;

- The European Commission according to our relevant contractual obligations.

8. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

9. Do we use cookies?

Our websites use cookies. Where cookies are used, a statement will be sent to your browser explaining the use of cookies.

Cookies are small text files which are saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet. They allow the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site. You can control and/ or delete cookies as you wish. If you do this, however, you may need to manually adjust your preferences every time you visit a site. For more information on how to manage cookies, please visit: <http://www.aboutcookies.org/>

We use tools like Google Analytics to better understand how visitors interact with our website. This provides us with important information to enable the site to work better. The information collected is not linked to your personal data. For more information on the cookies set by Google Analytics, please visit: <http://code.google.com/apis/analytics/docs/concepts/gaConceptsCookies.html>

The following cookies are necessary and are always enabled:

Name	Typical content	Cookie expires after
__cf_bm	The cookie is set by cloudflare. This cookie is used to distinguish between humans and bots. This is beneficial for the website, in order to make valid reports on the use of their website.	30 minutes
cookieLawInfo-checkbox-analytics	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Analytics".	11 months
cookieLawInfo-checkbox-functional	The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Functional".	11 months
cookieLawInfo-checkbox-necessary	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Necessary".	11 months
CookieLawInfoConsent	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie records the default button state of the corresponding category along with the status of CCPA.	11 months

Name	Typical content	Cookie expires after
viewed_cookie_policy	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.	11 months

The following cookies are functional and are always enabled:

Name	Typical content	Cookie expires after
wordpress_sec_COOKIEHASH	This cookie is set by wordpress. The cookie is set to provide protection against hackers, store account details.	session

The following cookies are for analytics and are optional:

Name	Typical content	Cookie expires after
ga*	This cookie is set by Google Analytics. This cookie is used to store and count pageviews.	2 years
_gat	Used to throttle request rate	1 minute
_ga	This cookie is set by Google Analytics. This cookie is used to distinguish users.	2 years

10. Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- **Right of access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.

- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** (see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm) regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by email: info@robin-project.eu. We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask from you some kind of identification (e.g., photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized reveal of your personal data. If, for reasons of complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

11. How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we have an obligation to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the end of the project (unless further retention is requested by auditors). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data in a secure manner.

12. Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with our project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used and disclosed by these sites.

13. Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under the age of 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16, we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately contact us if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

14. Revisions of this Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy is valid from 19/12/2022 and replaces any other previous notifications that we had issued in the past regarding our personal data management practices. We reserve the right to revise this Policy at any time. The current version will be always uploaded to our website indicating the date of entry into force, so you know when the most recent revision took place. If there are critical changes in this policy or our personal data practices change significantly in the future, we will notify you by posting the changes on our website.

9.2 Annex II – Informed Consent Form

Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text in grey colour contains examples and should be adjusted to the context of each activity.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

Before using this template take the time to carefully read and adjust it to the needs of the activity at hand as well as to any relevant regulations and particularities applicable to your country and organisation.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are < Insert Partner Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of ROBIN a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description on how ROBIN handles personal data is presented in the project's [Privacy Policy](#) available through the project's web page (www.robin-project.eu).

Project:

ROBIN - Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach (GA Number 101060504).

Partner:

Organisation name: < Insert Partner Name >

Address: < Insert Partner Address >.

Phone: < Insert Partner Phone >.

E-mail: <Insert Partner Generic E-mail Address >

Responsible persons:

You may delete the line referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	ROBIN Project Manager	<Insert name of project manager from your organisation>	<Insert e-mail of project manager from your organisation >
2	Interviewer	<Insert name of interviewer from your organisation >	<Insert e-mail of interviewer from your organisation >

3	Data Protection Officer	<Insert name of DPO from your organisation >	<Insert e-mail of DPO from your organisation >
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What do we need from you?

Please explain in a brief paragraph (4-5 lines) the activity and its purpose under the frame of the project.

Example: We need you to participate in an interview that will be carried out by ROBIN with a view to monitor and assess ROBIN's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change towards the new regional bioeconomy governance models.

The **interview** is expected to last for no more than < Insert number of minutes > minutes. We will take written notes **and we will be making a sound recording of the interview**.

Please adapt the following text to accurately depict the type of personal data to be collected.

To effectively conduct this **interview**, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number);
- Some basic demographics (age, gender);
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise);
- Your education info
- Your opinions on the subject matter.

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the aforementioned **interview** and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the **interview**. We also need to record your data to keep track of the **interview** process. The project's deliverables that will be derived by the **interview** will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes (**interview's transcript**) **and the sound recording** we will make during the **interview**.

We will share your data with a few other ROBIN project partners that are also involved in this task and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project's activities (e.g., surveys, interviews, project events etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g., by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the

informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in an interview that will be carried out by ROBIN to < insert key objective of the interview >	
2	My participation in future activities of ROBIN	
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding ROBIN activities	

Name of participant

Date

Signature

9.3 Annex III – Data Subject Request Form

Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

ROBIN

Data Subject Request form

You may delete the data referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

CONTACT

<Insert name of responsible Project Manager>	<Insert name of DPO > (Data Protection Officer)
<Insert email of responsible Project Manager>	<Insert e-mail of DPO >

DATA SUBJECT REQUEST FORM

This form should be used to submit a data subject request under the provisions of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Submitter Details

Title:	
Name:	
Address:	

TYPE OF REQUEST

Please select the type of request you are making:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Consent Withdrawal
<input type="checkbox"/>	Access request
<input type="checkbox"/>	Rectification of personal data
<input type="checkbox"/>	Erasure of personal data
<input type="checkbox"/>	Restriction of processing of personal data
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal data portability request
<input type="checkbox"/>	Objection to processing of personal data
<input type="checkbox"/>	Request regarding automated decision making and profiling

PERSONAL DATA INVOLVED

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REQUEST DETAILS

REQUEST REASON/JUSTIFICATION

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Once completed, this form should be submitted via e-mail to **< Insert contact e-mail of Partner >** or posted to:

< Insert Partner Name >

< Insert Partner Address >

9.4 Annex IV – Record of Processing Activities

Table 11: Record of Processing Activities

No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
1	Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	Desk research	WP1	Task 1.1	Potential MARC participants	Online databases	Information of candidate MARC members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile)	WR	All partners	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		All partners will support the process by providing candidates to WR.
2	Set up of ROBIN's Multi-Actor Regional Constellations	Networking	WP1	Task 1.1	Potential MARC participants	Data subject	Information of candidate MARC members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile)	WR	All partners	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		All partners will support the process by providing candidates to WR.
3	Identification of barriers, opportunities, and incentives of the Multi-Actor Regional Constellation to engage in circular bioeconomy governance	Interviews	WP1	Task 1.1	Interviewees	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Opinions, Demographics, Past experiences	WR			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
4	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Interviews	WP1	Task 1.4	Interviewees	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Opinions, Demographics, Past experiences	RCM			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		

D6.2: Data Management Plan – Initial Version, 28/02/2023

No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
5	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Interviews	WP1	Task 1.4	Interviewees	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Opinions, Demographics, Past experiences	SRA			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
6	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Interviews	WP1	Task 1.4	Interviewees	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Opinions, Demographics, Past experiences	CAP			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
7	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Interviews	WP1	Task 1.4	Interviewees	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Opinions, Demographics, Past experiences	ZSK			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
8	Analysis of the bioeconomy policy mix of the 5 ROBIN regions	Interviews	WP1	Task 1.4	Interviewees	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Opinions, Demographics, Past experiences	BPRO	S2I	Collection of personal contact data for some interviewees	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
9	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Workshop	WP2	Task 2.1	Workshop participants	Data subject	Opinions, Past experiences	RCM	CTA	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
10	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Workshop	WP2	Task 2.1	Workshop participants	Data subject	Opinions, Past experiences	SRA	CTA	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		

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No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
11	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Workshop	WP2	Task 2.1	Workshop participants	Data subject	Opinions, experiences Past	CAP	CTA	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
12	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Workshop	WP2	Task 2.1	Workshop participants	Data subject	Opinions, experiences Past	ZSK	CTA	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
13	Co-creation of the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders	Workshop	WP2	Task 2.1	Workshop participants	Data subject	Opinions, experiences Past	BPRO	CTA	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
14	Shaping of the Support Actions and Plans for each ROBIN region	Workshop	WP2	Task 2.2	Workshop participants	Data subject	Opinions, experiences Past	CTA	Regional authorities (i.e., RCM, SRA, CAP, ZSK, BPRO)	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
15	Data collected/generated by the utilisation of the ROBIN Toolbox	Use of ROBIN's digital Toolbox	WP2	Task 2.4	ROBINs digital Toolbox users	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Demographics, Past experiences, Knowledge	S2I	AUTH	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent, Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
16	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	Regional teams	WP3	Task 3.1	Regional teams' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information	BPRO	Regional authorities (i.e., RCM, SRA,	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		

D6.2: Data Management Plan – Initial Version, 28/02/2023

No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
									CAP, ZSK, BPRO)							
17	Elaboration of Toolbox Validation Plans	Testing teams	WP3	Task 3.1	Testing teams' participants	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Demographics, Past experiences	BPRO	Regional authorities (i.e., RCM, SRA, CAP, ZSK, BPRO)	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
18	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Testing sessions (Alpha)	WP3	Task 3.2	Testing sessions' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	BPRO	Regional authorities (i.e., RCM, SRA, CAP, ZSK, BPRO)	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent, Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
19	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Beta testings	WP3	Task 3.2	Beta testings' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	BPRO	Regional authorities (i.e., RCM, SRA, CAP, ZSK, BPRO)	Collection	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
20	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Stakeholder engagement events	WP3	Task 3.2	Events' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	RCM			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
21	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta	Stakeholder	WP3	Task 3.2	Events' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional	SRA			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		

D6.2: Data Management Plan – Initial Version, 28/02/2023

No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
	Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	engagement events					information, Opinions									
22	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Stakeholder engagement events	WP3	Task 3.2	Events' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	CAP			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
23	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Stakeholder engagement events	WP3	Task 3.2	Events' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	ZSK			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
24	Deployment of the Alpha and Beta Testing of the ROBIN Toolbox	Stakeholder engagement events	WP3	Task 3.2	Events' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	BPRO			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
25	Evaluation and Validation of Testing Results and fine-tuning of the ROBIN Toolbox	Validation workshop	WP3	Task 3.3	Workshop participants (AB members)	Data subject	Opinions, Past experiences	S2I	MTU, AUTH, QPL	Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
26	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Interviews	WP4	Task 4.1	Interviewees (MARC members)	Data subject	Opinions, insights, Past experiences	PED			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
27	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Survey	WP4	Task 4.1	Survey participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	RCM			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
28	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes,	Survey	WP4	Task 4.1	Survey participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	SRA			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		

D6.2: Data Management Plan – Initial Version, 28/02/2023

No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
	impacts and perceptions change															
29	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Survey	WP4	Task 4.1	Survey participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	CAP			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
30	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Survey	WP4	Task 4.1	Survey participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	ZSK			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
31	Monitoring and assessment of the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change	Survey	WP4	Task 4.1	Survey participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions	BPRO			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
32	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Knowledge exchange event	WP4	Task 4.2	Event's participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	RCM			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
33	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Knowledge exchange event	WP4	Task 4.2	Event's participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	SRA			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
34	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Knowledge exchange event	WP4	Task 4.2	Event's participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	CAP			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		

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No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
35	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Knowledge exchange event	WP4	Task 4.2	Event's participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	ZSK			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
36	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Knowledge exchange event	WP4	Task 4.2	Event's participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	BPRO			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
37	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Mutual learning workshops	WP4	Task 4.2	Workshops' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	CTA	ZSK, BPRO	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
38	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Mutual learning missions	WP4	Task 4.2	Missions' participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	CTA	ZSK, BPRO	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
39	Exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among the targeted regions	Train-the-Trainer event	WP4	Task 4.2	Event's participants	Data subject	Contact details Professional information, Opinions, knowledge	CTA			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
40	Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities	Dissemination of newsletter	WP5	Task 5.1	Newsletter subscribers	Data subject	Contact details	WR			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		

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No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
41	Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	Desk research	WP5	Task 5.2	Potential AB participants	Online databases	Contact details, Professional information, Demographics	WR	All partners	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		All partners will support the process by providing candidate AB members to WR.
42	Setup and Operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board	Networking	WP5	Task 5.2	Potential AB participants	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Demographics	WR	All partners	Collection, Use	No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		All partners will support the process by providing candidate AB members to WR.
43	Collaboration and Synergies with the CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives	Networking	WP5	Task 5.3	CCRI and Related Networks and Initiatives' officials	Data subject	Contact details, Professional information, Demographics	S2I			No	Art. 6(1)(a) - consent	No	No		
44	Project management, meetings and reporting	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	QPL			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
45	Project management, meetings and reporting	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	CTA			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
46	Project management, meetings and reporting	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	WR			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		

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No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
47	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	PED			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
48	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	S2I			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
49	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	ZSK			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
50	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	MTU			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
51	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	AUTH			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
52	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	RCM			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
53	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	CAP			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
54	Project management, meetings reporting and	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	IFA			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		

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No	Project Activity / purpose	Data processing activity	Linked WP(s)	Linked Task(s)	Data subjects	Data source	Data category(-ies)	Responsible partner	Involved partner(s)	Type of Involvement	Special category (Art. 9 GDPR)	Lawfulness of processing	Transfer to third countries (non EU-EEA)	Transfer to EU from third countries	Recipients	Comments
55	Project management, meetings and reporting	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	BPRO			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		
56	Project management, meetings and reporting	Project management	WP6	Task 6.1, Task 6.2, Task 6.3	Project partners	Data subject	Contact details Professional information Videos and photos	SRA			No	Art. 6(1)(b) - contract	No	No		

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the CCRI-CSO. We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

CONTACT US: info@robin-project.eu

VISIT: www.robin-project.eu

